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Author(s): Ioannis Kotsiopoulos and Angelos Yannopoulos (ED); Hayley Watson, Kush Wadhwa and Susan Anson (TRI); Alex Papadimitriou (HRT)
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report examines the use of new technologies to satisfy strategic communication goals of relevant stakeholders during crises. These are examined at three different levels, namely:

- ◆ among responders/law enforcement agencies
- ◆ between responders and the public
- ◆ among the public themselves

The findings regarding the strategic use of emerging technologies by different stakeholders will be used in conjunction with WP4, which focuses on emergency communication by the public.

The report includes three parts, one treating the strategic communication goals, another treating the interoperability issues facing social media today and their relevance to crisis management, and a third one presenting emergency response scenarios and the role of social media in them. As the first part has identified, there are four strategic goals relating to communication that are essential for stakeholders to be able to utilise communication to enhance their abilities to manage a crisis situation. These strategic goals include: two-way communication, one-way communication/alerts, information sharing, and situational awareness. Our findings show that each of these goals should not be treated in isolation, but rather, should be considered in relation to one another as, under some circumstances, they are dependent on each other for enhancing crisis management. For instance, during a flood, in order for the public to assist responders in gaining situational awareness, information sharing (e.g., photographs or video content), two-way communication (e.g., being able to verify information, or request further information) are essential to building situational awareness which in turn can contribute to decision making to help coordinate response efforts.

The second part treats interoperability of services and data among different social media platforms. The findings show that today we face a situation of “walled gardens” created and maintained by large platforms wanting to control information and to contain it among their members. However, although interoperability in the technical and the semantic sense has not been achieved, partial solutions via the platforms’ APIs have allowed some degree of inter-network communication and information retrieval, including users-related data. This has enabled the creation of a widely available number of network aggregator applications, which also has the beneficial effect of centralising social network information during a crisis.

The third part of the report shows scenarios on how new technologies can potentially meet these inter-connected strategic goals for each of these stakeholder groups across the different phases of a crisis. Scenarios for emergency response have to be based on field experience and information available to rescue organisations taking part in the course of a crisis incident. To this end, we examined the basic aspects of such scenarios from three points of view:

- The organisation’s mode of operation in specific events via their Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)
- The application of those to real-life situations as experienced by the COSMIC partner the Hellenic Rescue Team
- The contribution of weak signals and foresight to scenario building

In the first two areas, our findings show that the presence of social media appears particularly important. In the third area, we noted that there could be benefits for crisis management

regarding the existence of a methodological framework addressing the incorporation of weak signals in distress scenario building and in the early recognition of an incoming crisis.

The additional evidence supplied by Standard Operating Procedures of stakeholder responder organisations and the real-life situations confirm that social media:

- Provide help towards responders by completing the building of situational awareness
- Are able to supply additional information, in particular at the first stages of a catastrophic incident, which can be decisive in attracting external funds and sponsoring and therefore enabling the participation of voluntary organisations (NGOs) such as the HRT
- Can provide valuable information able to direct rescuers of survivors
- Are a means of publishing information towards the public concerning rescue efforts and other vital to life information

DRAFT

1 INTRODUCTION

This report examines the use of new technologies so as to satisfy strategic communication goals of relevant stakeholders during crises. These are examined at three different levels, namely:

- ◆ among responders/law enforcement agencies
- ◆ between responders and the public
- ◆ among the public themselves

The findings regarding the strategic use of emerging technologies by different stakeholders will be used in conjunction with WP4, which will focus on emergency communication by the public.

In the previous COSMIC Deliverable 2.1 on “*Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications*” we classified the operational states of social media under crises into the six fundamental functions listed below:

1. One-way communication (notify/alert)
2. Two-way communication (converse/provide feedback)
3. Request/offer assistance
4. Relay (share a piece of information with others)
5. Campaign (awareness raising/fund raising)
6. Organise (co-ordinate response/enable individuals to organise themselves)

In what follows, we analyse the strategic role of new communication technologies in these functions, the interoperability of services and data among different social media platforms and its strategic significance for social media aware crisis management. The report concludes with the essential elements of operating procedures, scenarios and processes applicable to response organisations.

2 STAKEHOLDER'S STRATEGIC GOALS

This chapter seeks to provide an overview of key strategic goals relating to the communication needs of three groups of stakeholders: among responders/law enforcement agencies, between responders and the public, and, among the public themselves. As will be discussed, at times, the following strategic goals are inter-related and should not be treated in isolation from one-another: two-way communication, one-way communications/alerts, information sharing, and situational awareness. In addition, partners will explore the importance of establishing partnerships between stakeholders for the improvement of services. Partners will use these strategic goals to discuss real-life scenarios that are central to these three groups of stakeholders in examining their communication-related needs and how emerging technologies may fulfil these during a crisis.

As outlined in D1.3 of the COSMIC project, communication is an essential element of crisis management,¹ albeit a complex challenge for the various stakeholders.² As argued by Vos et al. “in different phases of the crisis, the goal of communication is to reduce uncertainty about response, resolution, negative consequences, public perception, and blame of the situation”.³ As we have outlined elsewhere, it is essential to distinguish between risk and crisis communication during the different phases of a crisis.⁴ In the preparation and warning phase, communication is often in the form of risk communication; “the flow of information and risk evaluations back and forth between academic experts, regulatory practitioners, interest groups and the general public”.⁵ Alternatively, during the response and recovery phase, crisis communication occurs, referred to by Coombs as, “the collection, processing, and dissemination of information required to address a crisis situation”.⁶ Adequate communication is therefore essential for effective crisis management.

In order to identify these strategic goals, partners have conducted desk-based research to examine the key findings of other deliverables within the COSMIC project, as well as findings from other EU projects and relevant literature. The chapter concludes by identifying the criteria to be used for the development of scenarios in the remainder of this report.

2.1 AMONG RESPONDERS/LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES

First responders and law enforcement agencies include those stakeholders who are on the frontline of preparing for, responding to, and, recovering from a crisis. Within Europe these include: emergency services (e.g., police, fire and ambulance/health care providers), national and international non-governmental organisations (NGO's), local and national authorities and European bodies.⁷ As this sub-section will discuss, one and two-way communication,

¹ Blaha, Manfred, Marie-Christine Bonnamour, Robert Miskuf, David de Vries, Jelle Groenendaal and Ira Helsloot, “Report on the role of main stakeholders in crisis situations”, *Deliverable 1.3 of the COSMIC project*, December 2013

² Vos, Marita, Ragnhild Lund, Zvi Reich and Halliki Harro-Loit, *Developing a Crisis Communication Scorecard*. University Library of Jyväskylä, 2011.

³ Ibid., p. 17.

⁴ Blaha et al., 2013.

⁵ Leiss, William, *In the Chamber of Risks: Understanding Risk Controversies*. McGill Queens's University Press, Montreal, 1996, p. 388.

⁶ Coombs, W. Timothy, “Parameters for crisis communication”, in Coombs, W. Timothy and Sherry J. Holladay, (2011). *The Handbook of Crisis Communication*. John Wiley & Sons. [p. 20]

⁷ Blaha et al., 2013.

information sharing and situational awareness are central among responders/law enforcement agencies in the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis. The following table provides a summary of the strategic goals among responders/law enforcement agencies for each of the four stages of a crisis.

Table 1: Communication related strategic goals among responders/law enforcement agencies during the different stages of a crisis

	Two-way communication	Alert / One-way communication	Information sharing	Situational awareness
Preparation	X		X	
Warning	X	X	X	X
Response	X		X	X
Recovery	X		X	X

The preparation phase of a crisis involves “calamity arrangements with contingency plans as well as well-educated and trained emergency personnel and crisis management teams. Planning is helpful for determining what may happen when something goes wrong, and furthermore, what is needed in order to bring the situation back to a state of normalcy”.⁸ During the preparation phase of a crisis, as observed in D1.2, invariably, responders and law enforcement agencies need to communicate with one another via two-way communication to ensure that they have an effective crisis management plan in place. As will be seen in Section 2.5, an essential element is therefore the establishment and building of partnerships across different agencies to ensure the effective and efficient coordination of services in times of crisis.

In the warning phase of a crisis, responders and law enforcement agencies are often involved in alerting others to an imminent situation, and are reliant on one-way communication to alert other response organisations. For instance, the London Emergency Services Liaison Panel (LESLP), responsible for the cities Major Incident Manual, states that any member of LESLP can alert others and declare a major incident, subsequently, whilst the incident may not require the response of all members, they are all required to be on standby should their services be required.⁹ At this stage of a crisis, responders must also begin to share information about the nature and extent of the crisis with other response organisations to help begin to build situational awareness (SA).

SA involves “knowing what is going on around you”.¹⁰ Although debated, a “general definition of SA” concerns “the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future”.¹¹ Within the management of crises, as will be seen in the subsequent paragraph, SA is essential to responders’ efforts in being able to respond to the growing demands of a crisis and to inform and complement decision making.¹² In addition, adequate decision-making can help build SA.¹³ Accordingly, following the initial alert, as the

⁸ Watson, Hayley, Kush Wadhwa, Jelle Groenendaal, David de Vries and Alex Papadimitriou, “Report on search and rescue actions”, *Deliverable 1.2 of the COSMIC project*, September 2013b. [p. 8]

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Endsley, Mica. R, “Theoretical Underpinnings of Situation Awareness: A Critical Review”, in Endsley, Mica R., and Daniel J. Garland, “Situation Awareness Analysis and Measurement”, 2000, pp. 3–32. [p. 5]

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Ibid.

immediate realisation and understanding of the crisis builds two-way communication and information sharing is required between responders to begin co-ordination.

The response phase of a crisis involves the initial emergency response, which often includes search and rescue operations to be carried out by responders and law enforcement agencies.¹⁴ The response period calls for effective two-way communication and decision making to respond to the demands of the situation and crucially, to help gain a level of control over any uncertainties that may have appeared as a result of the crisis. Not only is it important for effective two-way communication to occur for those within a single organisation, but also for interagency communications. For instance, as identified in D1.2, following the 2005 London attacks, in order to respond to the crisis, it was essential for official bodies (i.e., the different stakeholders involved in LESLP) to quickly gain footing, as well as a continual understanding of the unfolding situation including for instance, the number of explosions, potential casualties and any other potential targets.¹⁵ Thus, both single agency communication and interagency information sharing is required to enable decision making and response efforts to progress, both of which require efficient two-way communication.¹⁶ However, interagency information sharing is often hampered by the lack of procedures and systematic information management in many agencies, as well as interoperable information formats.

In the aftermath of a crisis, for responders and law enforcement agencies, the recovery phase of a crisis involves “all activities aimed at bringing the evolved situation back to normalcy, from rebuilding activities to providing compensation for damage. This phase also encompasses learning from (near-) disasters, providing feedback to other links in the chain and thus making societies less vulnerable to similar events in the future”.¹⁷ In this period, as well as continuing recovery efforts, agencies are involved in a period of knowledge discovery, requiring two-way communication, information sharing and active reflection to identify and build upon lessons learned. As shown in D1.2, learning from a crisis is essential to improving crisis management, however, there are challenges involved including; the desire to share lessons learned, and being able to compare these lessons across different countries and/or agencies.¹⁸

2.2 BETWEEN RESPONDERS AND THE PUBLIC

In the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis, responders and members of the public are closely tied. As part of their responsibilities for managing a crisis, responders must form a trusting relationship with the public to ensure that they are adequately prepared for, and able to respond to and recover from a crisis. Within this context, the term “responders” includes organisations such as national agencies, law enforcement agencies and civil society organisations involved in managing the potential impact of a crisis on members of the public. Members of the public are, in part, reliant on responders for providing them with detailed, accurate and up-to-date information during all stages of a crisis. Likewise, responders are somewhat reliant on members of the public for, where possible, feeding them information during the response phase of a crisis. As such, there is a symbiotic relationship between the two in the effective management of crises. Accordingly, as this sub-section will discuss, all

¹⁴ Watson et al., 2013b.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Blaha et al., 2013.

¹⁷ Watson et al., 2013b, p. 9.

¹⁸ Blaha et al., 2013.

four strategic goals; one and two-way communication, information sharing and SA are crucial to maintaining an effective working relationship between responders and members of the public in the preparation, response and recovery of a crisis. The following table provides a summary of the strategic goals between responders and the public for each of the four stages of a crisis.

Table 2: Communication related strategic goals between responders and the public during the different stages of a crisis

	Two-way communication	Alert / One-way communication	Information sharing	Situational awareness
Preparation	X		X	
Warning		X	X	X
Response	X	X	X	X
Recovery	X		X	X

During the preparation phase of a crisis, responders participate in risk communication activities. As identified by Steelman and McCaffrey, risk communication “seeks to inform people about a potential future harm and the associated dangers so that they might take action to mitigate the risk”.¹⁹ A key communication related strategic goal, which is often a challenge at this time, includes information sharing activities.²⁰ That is their ability to adequately inform and educate those likely to be affected by a crisis (e.g., members of the public) with crisis related information in order to help them enhance their resilience. As identified in D1.1, such a task is complex as it is dependent on a number of social factors which may contribute to a person’s attitude to risk and thus, will impact how effective their responsive risk communication is. As such, a number of social and demographic related variables (e.g., age, gender, past experience etc.) must be taken into consideration.²¹

Furthermore, as outlined in D1.3, it is essential that the public have an understanding of their roles and responsibilities in a crisis, which will subsequently help to boost crisis management efforts and effectiveness; this therefore requires two-way communication and effective information sharing to help educate the public. Educating the public about disaster management involves: informing them of any potential risks they may face and how they can be mitigated, educating them about the characteristics of disasters, informing them how best to respond to different types of disasters and providing them with an understanding of how they can support responders in a crisis.²² For instance, in some parts of the US, in response to the growing threat from wildfires, Community Wildfire Protection Plans have been developed to help homeowners during such an event.^{23, 24} Similarly, during the 2012 California wildfires, social media was seen to be an essential tool for one-way communication, enabling authorities to alert members of the public in the affected area.²⁵

¹⁹ Steelman, Toddi A, and Sarah McCaffrey, “Best Practices in Risk and Crisis Communication: Implications for Natural Hazards Management”, *Natural Hazards*, Vol. 65, No. 1, 2013, pp. 683–705. [p. 689]

²⁰ Blaha et al., 2013.

²¹ Watson et al., 2013a.

²² Ibid., p. 20.

²³ Steelman and McCaffrey, 2013, p. 688.

²⁴ As will be discussed in the second version of this deliverable, community building is also essential to the preparation phases of a crisis, where for instance, building an online community prior to a crisis occurring can help to ensure information is disseminated as and when a crisis occurs.

²⁵ Papadimitriou, Alex, Angelos Yannopoulos, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Rachel L. Finn, Kush Wadhwa, Hayley Watson and Lemi Baruh, “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project*, 30 September 2013.

During the warning phase of a crisis, responders continue to participate in risk and crisis communication activities relating to information sharing, where they must, in a timely fashion, adequately inform the public of any impending crises that they may be vulnerable to. During this stage, their primary goal is to ensure that the public are alerted to the dangers, including a clear understanding of the nature and timeline of the threat, what action should be taken and any other relevant information to ensure their safety is shared, and that the public can immediately begin to build their own SA and respond accordingly. As discussed in D2.2, the use of alerting systems and social media as an alerting mechanism was seen during the 2013 UK heat wave where the UK's Met Office used Twitter and Facebook to send out weather related alerts to members of the public.²⁶ As such, one-way communication in the form of an “alert”, as well as the sharing of crucial information, is essential to building SA in the immediate warning phase of a crisis.

Furthermore, during the response phase of a crisis, just as members of the public are reliant on responders for sharing information to help them build their SA, so too are responders reliant on members of the public to provide them with information to help them build their own SA.²⁷ As identified in D1.3, information gathering from the public is integral to response activities.²⁸ For instance, following the 2013 Boston marathon attacks, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) used their Twitter account to request photographs and video footage to be sent to them by those at the scene of the attacks. Similarly, following Hurricane Sandy in the US in 2012, response organisations requested information from the public to help build their SA.²⁹

During the response phase, as extensively discussed in D2.3, it is also essential for responders to monitor the sharing of information which will help to ensure that misinformation and other activity which could impact the reliability of information is identified, and that accordingly, the correct facts can be passed along to the public.³⁰ For instance, as argued by the Queensland Police in their experience of using social media to quell rumours following the floods caused by Tropical Cyclone Tasha in December 2010, both one and two-way communication can be an effective way of “mythbusting”.³¹

Furthermore, on-going communication with the public surrounding the status of events is crucial; at this point whilst one-way communication in the form of updates is useful, so too is ensuring two-way communication continues to take place to establish a form of dialogue between responders and the public. For instance, following the eruption of the Eyjafjallajökull volcano in 2010, the European Organisation for the Safety of Air Navigation (EUROCONTROL), used social media applications (e.g., YouTube, Facebook and Twitter) to communicate with airlines and members of the public throughout the crisis. By doing so they were able to play a significant role in conversing with passengers throughout the period of disruption and to help them respond accordingly.³²

²⁶ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

²⁷ Queensland Police, “Social Media Case Study”, Queensland Police Website, 2013. <http://www.police.qld.gov.au/services/reportsPublications/other/socialmedia.htm>

²⁸ Blaha et al., 2013.

²⁹ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

³⁰ Scifo, Salvatore, and Lemi Baruh, “Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media”, *Deliverable 2.3 of the COSMIC project*, November 2013.

³¹ Queensland Police, 2013, p. 5.

³² Watson, Hayley, and Rachel L. Finn, “Privacy and ethical implications of the use of social media during a volcanic eruption: some initial thoughts”, *Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference*, Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013.

The response phase of a crisis may also be met with extensive volunteerism. During such a time, it is often the case that response agencies are inundated with generous offers of help and assistance from members of the public. For instance, following the terrorist attacks in the USA in September 2001, extensive numbers of individuals offered their assistance.³³ As such, during this time it was essential for responders to be able to communicate with the public via two-way communication, manage volunteers and essentially, put the services that the public offered to good use. Crucially, being able to offer some assistance in a crisis, may for some, fulfil a psychological role in enabling them to achieve social-psychological goals, including helping to establish a sense of connectedness and assisting them in managing the psychological impact of the crisis.³⁴ As such, communication is required to optimise the use of volunteers in the response to a crisis.

Lastly, during the recovery phases of a crisis, continued open and reliable two-way communication between responders and the public is a priority, not only to ensure that the affected community is kept up-to-date with recovery efforts, but in addition, to include those affected by a crisis in identification and dissemination of lessons learned.³⁵

2.3 AMONG THE PUBLIC

As with the other stakeholders examined in this chapter, communication is central to the preparation, response and recovery efforts among members of the public as a result of a crisis. The following table provides a summary of the strategic goals for each of the four stages of a crisis.

Table 3: Communication related strategic goals among the public during the different stages of a crisis

	Two-way communication	Alert / One-way communication	Information sharing	Situational awareness
Preparation	X	X		
Warning	X	X	X	X
Response	X	X	X	X
Recovery	X		X	X

In preparing for a crisis, members of the public are able to share information they receive from official sources to others in their social networks. In order to do so, one and two-way communication is essential. As argued by FEMA’s “Fundamentals of Emergency Management”, preparedness is not simply the responsibility of response organisations, but in addition, members of the public can take measures to ensure that they adequately prepare themselves and their families to take steps to prepare for an emergency.³⁶ By informally sharing preparation strategies with others, the public can play a role in helping to share good practices within a community.

During the warning phases of a crisis both one and two-way communication continues to be pivotal to share news of an impending crisis with others in their social networks. Such

³³ Lowe, Seana, and Alice Fothergill, “A Need to Help: Emergent Volunteer Behavior after September 11th”, *Beyond September 11th: An Account of Post-Disaster Research*, 2003, pp. 293–314.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Blaha et al., 2013.

³⁶ FEMA, *Fundamentals of Emergency Management*, 2010.

communication activities enable members of the public to inform each other of emerging events which helps them enhance their SA and overall resilience to a crisis.

During the response phase of a crisis members of the public may continue to use one and two-way communication to share insights, experiences and information with others in their social networks. For instance, following the Boston attacks members of the public used social media to share information with others relating to road closures and police activities, which helped to build SA among those caught up in the crisis.³⁷ Elsewhere, during the Gezi protests, members of the public used social media to share information with others in their social networks, and many relied on social media for updates rather than the traditional media which was viewed as biased in its reporting. As such, one and two-way communication among the public helped to ensure the spread of what was deemed more reliable information which subsequently helped to build SA within the affected community.³⁸

During the response stage of a crisis there is also the danger of miscommunication and the widespread sharing of rumours among members of the public. However, as experienced during the Virginia Tech shootings in 2007, members of the public participated in collective problem solving to help ensure that reliable information was shared via social networking sites.³⁹ As remarked in their study of a Facebook group that participated in problem solving activities, the use of social media by members of the public were conducted in a “concentrated, well-intentioned, and earnest fashion” where instead of “rumor-mongering, we see socially-produced accuracy”.⁴⁰ Thus, during the response stage of a crisis, members of the public can work together to help share information that disputes rumours, thereby helping to mitigate any further diffusion of rumours, and they can therefore, contribute to sharing reliable information.

Lastly, during the recovery stage of a crisis, two-way communication and the sharing of information continues to be important to enable members of the public to learn from each other’s experiences and to cope and recover. Not only does this help to continue to maintain SA, but, in addition, two-way communication may help to fulfil a psychological role during a crisis as it enables members of the public to actively participate in recovery efforts.

2.4 ESTABLISHING PARTNERSHIPS BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS

Partnerships are central to optimising the use of social media as part of an effective crisis communication strategy. The term partnership relates to a joint interest between different individuals or groups, and a sense of action in terms of actively participating and working together to achieve a mutually beneficial goal.⁴¹ Within the study of emergency management, partnerships are commonly discussed in relation to collective action and collaboration.

³⁷ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Vieweg, Sarah, Leysia Palen, Sophia B. Liu, Amanda L. Hughes and Jeannette Sutton, “Collective Intelligence in Disaster: An Examination of the Phenomenon in the Aftermath of the 2007 Virginia Tech Shootings”, *Proceedings of the 5th International ISCRAM Conference*, Washington, DC, USA, 2008.

⁴⁰ Ibid., 2008, p. 10.

⁴¹ Dictionary.com, “partnership”, Unabridged. Random House, Inc, 2014.
<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/partnership>

As identified by Waugh Jnr. and Streib, in the US, the field of emergency management, based around collaboration activities has been around since the 1940s/1950s.⁴² As time progressed and a multi-hazard approach to emergency management was adopted in the 1990s, the challenges relating to managing relationships across governmental and non-governmental organisations were also realised. A key component of emergency management became, and continues to be, effective collaboration between different stakeholders required to respond to an emergency.⁴³ As identified in COSMIC Deliverable 1.2, during the 2005 London terrorist attacks, it was necessary for different emergency services in London, as well as local authorities, transport providers and hospitals to collaborate with one another in order to manage resources across the multiple scenes.⁴⁴

Not restricted to professional organisations responding to a crisis, the affected community are also important in collaborative efforts to engage and respond to a crisis. As outlined by Waugh Jnr. and Streib, following a crisis, members of the affected community (and at times those from outside) converge at the site of a crisis in order to offer their assistance.⁴⁵ Consequently, collaboration and partnerships are not simply required between those experts involved in response efforts, but also volunteers (as also discussed in Section 2.2 – above). As such there is a need to consider the different types of partnerships between different stakeholders that are necessary for enhancing the capacity to prepare for, respond to and recover from a crisis through crisis communication.

In Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project, partners identified numerous instances of the need for stakeholders to work together in an emergency in order to use new media, particularly social media, to engage with those caught up in a crisis. For instance, following the 2013 Boston attacks, we saw the Boston police department use twitter to engage with individuals present at the scene of the attacks and to request that the public share information such as photographs.⁴⁶ Furthermore, following the missing Malaysia Airlines flight MH370, crowdsourcing activities of over 2 million people searching through satellite imagery as organised by Tomnod, a commercial satellite company, provides further evidence of the importance of partnerships involving the public, particularly the growing community of digital volunteers.⁴⁷ Such efforts require effective and long-standing partnerships, particularly in meeting strategic goals relating to two-way communication, information sharing and building situational awareness. As such, within this current sub-section, we will therefore consider why there is a need for establishing partnerships between different stakeholders within crisis management.

Among responders/law enforcement

As discussed in Section 2.1 above, it is important for responders, as well as those involved in law enforcement to work together in order to provide an effective, harmonised response to a crisis. As argued by Kapucu, during a crisis, interaction between different responders and law enforcement does not solely occur amongst senior members of staff, but also amongst lower

⁴² Waugh, William L., and Gregory Streib, “Collaboration and Leadership for Effective Emergency Management,” *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 66, No. s1, December 2006, pp. 131–140. <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00673.x>.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Watson et al., 2013.

⁴⁵ Waugh and Streib, 2006.

⁴⁶ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

⁴⁷ Fishwick, Carmen, “Tomnod – the Online Search Party Looking for Malaysian Airlines Flight MH370,” *The Guardian*, 14 March 2014. <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/mar/14/tomnod-online-search-malaysian-airlines-flight-mh370>.

levels of staff, and thus effective interagency communication is essential to crisis management efforts.⁴⁸

In his study of interagency communication during the 11th September 2001 terror attacks in the US, Kapucu found that inter-organisational communication and interoperable communication systems were essential for facilitating a coordinated response. He found that problems with communication between the New York Police Department and the Fire Department of New York were typical in responding to the attacks, and that such problems were compounded by issues of compatibility in radio systems between the two organisations.⁴⁹ Furthermore, interviews conducted with emergency personnel during the study, revealed that 74% of the sample claimed that cooperation between organisations was of use in serving the community, and a further 61% felt that a partnership between organisations was essential for facilitating the provision of services in an emergency.⁵⁰ Of those interviewed, non-profit organisations were most concerned with the need for greater partnerships. Further results from the study show that on-going efforts are required among different organisations in order to collaboratively respond to a disaster; “Information must be shared by the organisations, and activities must be coordinated within and across organisational boundaries”.⁵¹ Examples of information sharing and the coordination of activities both within and across organisational boundaries were identified during the Disaster 2.0 research project.⁵² For example, during the 2012 forest fires in Spain there was significant damage to critical infrastructure. Subsequently, the public provided information on critical infrastructure failure to the Catalonian Civil Protection Service via their Twitter accounts.⁵³ This information was then shared with the relevant departments to enable them to address the damage reported by the public.

The findings of the Disaster 2.0 project (whose findings are also examined in Chapter 3) also highlighted how the strategic use of social media technologies can increase the effectiveness of partnerships between the different crisis management stakeholders. Drawing again on the case of the Catalonian Civil Protection Service, their Twitter account was identified as a hub of information for different stakeholders including local emergency services, weather forecasters and transit services.⁵⁴ In addition to accessing their information, these stakeholders would also regularly send their messages to the Civil Protection Service in order to receive support in spreading the message. During the 2012 forest fires, the Civil Protection Service also used Twitter strategically to manage their relationship with journalists. In order to reduce the time spent explaining information to individual journalists, they used their Twitter account as a substitute for communicating with the journalists by telephone.⁵⁵

Elsewhere in the COSMIC project, as discussed in D1.2, in 1973 the London Emergency Services Liaison Panel (LESLP) was formed, consisting of representatives from the different

⁴⁸ Kapucu, Naim, “Interagency Communication Networks During Emergencies: Boundary Spanners in Multiagency Coordination,” *The American Review of Public Administration*, Vol. 36, No. 2, June 1, 2006, pp. 207–225. <http://arp.sagepub.com/content/36/2/207>.

⁴⁹ Ibid., p. 214.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Ibid., p. 221.

⁵² Beneito-Montagut, Roser, Duncan Shaw and Christopher Brewster, “Disaster 2.0 Case studies: Using Web 2.0 applications and Semantic Technologies to strengthen public resilience to disasters”, *Deliverable of the Disaster 2.0 project*, 2013.

⁵³ Ibid., p.27.

⁵⁴ Ibid., p.27.

⁵⁵ Ibid., p.26.

emergency services, local authorities, voluntary sector organisations and military branches.⁵⁶ The group continue to meet every three months, and as part of their efforts in preparing for a major incident in the capital, have developed and continue to revise their “Major Incident Procedure Manual”. The building of partnerships between the different stakeholders involved in LESLP, is crucial to achieving strategic communication goals, particularly in relation to effective two-way communication, information sharing and the building of situational awareness. Following the terrorist attacks in London in 2005, multi-agency coordination was essential. As with the example provided by Kapucu, D1.2 demonstrates that due to problems in communication devices, agencies experienced difficulty communicating with one another, as well as problems in coordinating resources, and the establishment of a survivors reception area (which, according to the Major Incident Procedure Manual should be initiated in order to record the details of those affected by a major incident).⁵⁷ Once again, the need for a coordinated effort is evident.

Not only is there a need for the building of relationships between emergency services, but in addition, efforts can be made to support the establishment of partnerships between different types of organisations involved in crisis management activities. For instance, as revealed in D2.2 of the COSMIC project, “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, a partnership between the UKs Met Office (responsible for weather updates) and Cancer Research UK (a charity focusing on cancer research) was utilised to develop social media content for YouTube.⁵⁸ Through this joint effort, educational videos were created to help prepare and warn the public of the potential harmful effects from a heatwave. Such a partnership is useful in providing useful information and interactive content to engage with the public. Accordingly, it is not enough that effective partnerships exist between responders, but in addition, there is a need for partnerships between responders and the public.

Between responders and the public

An important component to preparing the public for the possibility of a crisis, as well as engaging with the public in the response and recovery of a crisis is the communication of information, and as such, it is imperative that responders develop and maintain relationships with communities.

Much of this responsibility lies with those responsible for communicating with the public. As identified in Deliverable 2.2 of the COSMIC project, civil society organisations are able to contribute to efforts in preparing the public for a crisis, as demonstrated during the 2013 UK heatwave (discussed above). Furthermore, as outlined in their “Communicating with the Public Framework”, the London Resilience Partnership outlined how relationships can also be valuable between responders, including those in local authorities and local businesses, to ensure that timely and efficient information and action takes place in the event of a crisis.⁵⁹ In responding to a crisis, the London Resilience Partnership appropriately claim that social media is useful for building relationships. However, little, if any, information is given in their framework on how this should take place; rather emphasis is placed on the use of social media in the event of an incident. Consequently, further information and guidance is required on how these tools can be used for fostering relationships with the public.

⁵⁶ Watson et al., 2013.

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

⁵⁹ London Resilience Partnership, “Communicating with the Public Framework”, 2014. <https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Communicating%20with%20the%20Public%20Framework%20v1.0%20web.pdf>

In addition to partnerships between responders and the public being useful for preparing for a crisis, this type of partnership is also valuable for information sharing and the building of situational awareness in a crisis. During a crisis, in the past, the public were predominantly reliant on emergency services and the press for information regarding unfolding events. However, this is no longer the case. As examined throughout the COSMIC project, the public are also able to play an important role in feeding information to responders to help build situational awareness. For instance, following the Boston marathon attacks in 2013, the Massachusetts Emergency Management Agency utilised Wireless Emergency Alerts to send alerts to members of the public in the affected area, subsequently, these alerts were further amplified by members of the public via social media.⁶⁰ The public also further circulated information shared by civil society organisations, event organisers and the emergency services via social media. Furthermore, the Federal Bureau of Investigation engaged with crowdsourcing techniques to call upon the public to share information, particularly photographs and videos of the scene of the attacks in order to build their evidence of the scene in order to assist them in identifying those responsible.⁶¹ Digital volunteer groups also participated in the online emergency response to the Boston marathon attacks that occurred during the Social Media and Semantic Technologies in Emergency Response (SMERST) conference held as part of the Disaster 2.0 project.⁶² Three conference participants active in multiple digital volunteer groups (e.g., Crisismappers, Standby Task Force and Geeks Without Bounds) spent the night gathering and confirming information to support the response to the attacks. As such, trusting relationships between the public, including digital volunteer groups and responders is essential in the circulation of information in the event of a crisis.

In recovering from a crisis, the on-going building of trusting relationships is important for the affected community to return to a state of normalcy as quickly as possible. Once again, open communication is essential. The Disaster 2.0 project identified examples of how social media was used by responders to communicate to the public that an incident was over and that the situation had returned to normal. For instance, following the 2011 riots that took place in several UK cities, including Wolverhampton, West Midlands Police used Twitter to reassure the public that the riots were over and that a state of normalcy and safety had returned.⁶³ This involved senior Police staff tweeting messages, including: “In Wolverhampton city centre, great feeling, no problems at all” and “Just been for a walk around town on my lunch break – I have lots of photos to share with you – no problem anywhere that I could see and I walked from...”.⁶⁴ Social media was also used by London Fire Brigade during the 2012 Olympic Games to provide reassurance to the public concerning an incident that they were responding to.⁶⁵ London Fire Brigade had received images of a fire at “Kiwi House” where many fans of the New Zealand Olympic team were based. Social media was used to provide reassurance to the public that the situation was under control and that everyone was safe. Thus, social media can be used to facilitate the return to a state of normalcy through its ability to communicate information to the public that both reassures them and that confirms that the crisis is over.

Between responders/law enforcement agencies, the public and the R&D community

⁶⁰ Papadimitriou et al., 2013.

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² Beneito-Montagut et al., 2013.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Ibid., p.95.

⁶⁵ Beneito-Montagut et al., 2013.

In light of the growing importance of information communication technology, including social media, to communication efforts in a crisis, it is essential for working-relationships to be built between the emergency services and the research and development (R&D) community. As identified in Deliverable 2.1, “Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications”, there is an extensive number of applications being developed for communicating information, each providing different functionality for preparing for, responding to and recovering from a crisis.⁶⁶ With such an abundance of activity in the IT sector, it is necessary for the two parties to work together to ensure that tools are being developed, and that existing systems, are being enhanced in such a manner that meets stakeholder needs.

For instance, the London Air Ambulance Service in collaboration with developers, recently developed and rolled out two mobile applications, GoodSAM, that enable 1) locally qualified and registered responders, to be alerted to the scene of an accident requiring assistance; and 2) for anyone to request help. Furthermore, the system is interoperable with emergency dispatch so that the ambulance service can automatically notify local qualified and registered responders.⁶⁷ Such an example of collaboration between stakeholders is imperative to aid the growing demands for support that is placed on the ambulance service, and enables those trained in first aid to utilise their skills for the greater good. A similar initiative exists in the Netherlands, which engages those members of the public with first aid training.⁶⁸ Going forward, if civil society organisations also engage with this development and work alongside existing partners, they too can support this need (e.g., by encouraging the uptake of this tool amongst the public and encouraging additional trained personnel to register as responders). A mobile application created by The National Institute of Geophysics & Volcanology (INGV) in Italy also facilitated collaboration between different stakeholders. The mobile application works in collaboration with an INGV webpage, www.haisentitoilterremoto.it (“I have felt an earthquake”) and requests that the public who have felt an earthquake provide information on their experience via the webpage or the mobile application.⁶⁹ INGV then use this information to build a map of the earthquakes that are felt by the public. This is an example on the social media assisted role of citizens as journalists-reporters (sensors), whose characteristics have been analysed in COSMIC deliverable 4.1.1.⁷⁰

Consequently, when we consider the importance of partnerships within crisis management, as briefly examined within this chapter, the fostering of relationships between different types of stakeholders is essential for crisis management efforts.

2.5 CONCLUSION

As this chapter has identified, there are four strategic goals relating to communication that are essential for stakeholders to be able to utilise communication to enhance their abilities to manage a crisis situation. These strategic goals include: two-way communication, one-way communication/alerts, information sharing, and situational awareness. As highlighted in the

⁶⁶ Watson, Hayley, Rachel L Finn, Kush Wadhwa, and A Yannopoulos, “Baseline Analysis of Communication Technologies and their Applications”, *Deliverable 2.1 of the COSMIC project*, 2013.

⁶⁷ GoodSAM app, 2014. <https://www.goodsamapp.org/home>

⁶⁸ SOS Alarm, 2014. <http://www.helplevensredden.nl>

⁶⁹ Beneito-Montagut et al., 2013.

⁷⁰ Lemi Baruh, Alex Papadimitriou, Zeynep Günel, Haluk Mert Bal, Yusuf Salman, Salvatore Scifo, Büşra Çildaş “Report on citizens’ involvement in emergency communication”, *Deliverable D4.1.1, COSMIC project*, 2014

sub-sections above, each of these goals should not be treated in isolation, but rather, should be considered in relation to one another as, under some circumstances, they are dependent on each other for enhancing crisis management. For instance, during a flood, in order for the public to assist responders in gaining situational awareness, information sharing (e.g., photographs or video content), two-way communication (e.g., being able to verify information, or request further information) are essential to building situational awareness which in turn can contribute to decision making to help coordinate response efforts. The figure below provides further information on the inter-relationships of strategic goals.

Figure 1: Scenario criteria

In the remainder of this report, partners will examine the last two horizontal areas of the diagramme above, by examining interoperability among services and data for social media platforms and scenarios on how existing and emerging technologies, can potentially meet these inter-connected strategic goals for these stakeholder groups across the different phases of a crisis, whilst maintaining the integrity of the quality of data and communication.

3 INTEROPERABILITY AMONG SYSTEMS AND DATA

An achievement of the 90s in ICT was the emergence and wide acceptance of open standards, as opposed to the previously dominant proprietary technologies for hardware, software and data. As analysed in deliverable D3.2.1,⁷¹ open standards primarily refer to standardisation of compatibility throughout the evolving lifecycles of the addressed technologies.

Open standards have provided significant help towards the cause of the Internet itself. The origins of the World Wide Web, such as early forums for programmers to exchange code, as well as its later evolution to freely available information on products, news or ideas are all based on openness and access by all. This situation is however at risk of being overturned ironically by those who have appeared as advocates of free flows of information and content. As Patty Donovan from the Open Group observed:⁷²

- “... With the advent of Web 2.0, content no longer roams free. Increasingly, private companies and social networks, such as Facebook and Google Plus, have realised the value of controlling information and restricting the once open flow of the Internet. A link to a Facebook profile, for example, doesn’t lead to a member’s Facebook page, but instead to an invitation to join Facebook – a closed, member-only network where one must be inside the network to derive any benefit. And once one joins one of these “walled gardens,” personal content is shared in ways that are uncontrollable by the user...”

The phenomenon becomes even more pronounced with the ever increasing flows of such personal content. In deliverable D3.2.1 we identified two largely unsolved issues regarding open standards in such environments⁷¹:

- standardisation of social media data
- standardisation of technical means for interacting with social media services

Regarding social media data, we remarked⁷¹ that its distinguishing features compared to Web 1.0, such as:

- intrinsic inter-referencing, due to the handling of relationships
- entities involved in these relationships are mostly real-world entities, such as people, therefore representations are at best semi-structured⁷³
- vast amounts of regularly generated data
- richness in semantics (due to feature 2 above) and in digital media content (images, videos, sound)

pose a considerable challenge. Manual examination of social media content is generally out of the question due to its sheer volume, therefore machine-readable modelling of the semantic relationships and of the representation of such content (data) is needed. This can eventually lead to semantic interoperability (in the sense of the European Interoperability Framework

⁷¹ I. Kotsiopoulos, A. Yannopoulos, H. Watson, R. Finn, K. Wadhwa, A. Papadimitriou, “Political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies”, Deliverable 3.2.1, COSMIC, October 2013

⁷² Patty Donovan, “Social Networks – Challenging an Open Internet? Walled Gardens Tweet Jam”, The Open Group Blog, July 9, 2012, 2:56 pm, <http://blog.opengroup.org/2012/07/09/social-networks-challenging-an-open-internet-facebook-walled-gardens-tweet-jam>

⁷³ Using “likes”, tags, and many other relationship realisations.

2.0⁷⁴) for social media data. The importance of such a capability when it comes to crises data is self-evident: a network-independent way of extracting meaning out of social media communication could revolutionise our way of utilising information during the onset of a crisis and our way of responding to it.

On the side of the interaction with social media services, we remarked⁷¹ that open standards, such as for example OpenSocial⁷⁵, Activity Streams⁷⁶ and others have not been adopted by established major players such as Facebook and Twitter, although aspiring competitors such as Google, Yahoo! and IBM often promote them as a means of gaining a piece of the “pie”. The reality is that the social media world today remains without commonly applicable open standards for social media services and consequently with poor technical interoperability (in the sense of the European Interoperability Framework 2.0⁷⁴). The business model of large networks, which aims at attracting and simultaneously reaping value from their membership, is a significant contributor to this state of affairs. This lack of inter-network sharing does not affect the general communication needs of the ordinary user: in most cases communities of interest have already been formed and multiple memberships to major networks are common. When it comes to critical circumstances use however, for example crises, wide inter-network dissemination and extraction of information cannot happen without us overcoming the fragmentation created by today’s network and online communities’ silos.

3.1 A STRATEGIC PERSPECTIVE

As D. Hinchcliffe remarked on ZDNet,⁷⁷ a current aspiration for social media would be for them to become far more standardised, automatically interoperable, and under our full control. Put in other words by the same source: “...the benefits of open standards are potentially quite considerable: All our data would be open in any social network, we could export our contacts and conversations whenever we want, we could easily find knowledge anywhere it lies any social system, and innovative new social tools would be easier to adopt because they talk to everything else already (and I do mean everything, since standards like OpenSocial⁷⁸ mean even all our applications are integrated into the social fabric)...”

When faced with the role of social networks during a crisis, the above vision becomes far more important. A distress message or a critical piece of information could be exported to all social media, and retrieval of critical information by rescue and response organisations could take place in a far more automated and immediate manner. The reason for this is that extraction of relevant, potentially life-saving knowledge – being made (at least) semi-readable by machines due to its semantically interoperable structure – would have the potential to become a regular feature of the virtual social discourse.

⁷⁴ European Commission, Annex 2 to the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions 'Towards interoperability for European public services, Bruxelles, 16 December 2010, COM(2010) 744 final, http://ec.europa.eu/isa/documents/isa_annex_ii_eif_en.pdf

⁷⁵ OpenSocial and Gadgets Specification Group, “OpenSocial Core Data Specification 2.5.1”, <http://opensocial.github.io/spec/2.5.1/Core-Data.xml>

⁷⁶ <http://activitystrea.ms>

⁷⁷ Hinchcliffe D., “How we can create open standards for social business”, ZDNet, Enterprise Web 2.0, 27 June 2013, <http://www.zdnet.com/how-we-can-create-open-standards-for-social-business-7000017420>

⁷⁸ OpenSocial and Gadgets Specification Group, “OpenSocial Core Data Specification 2.5.1”, <http://opensocial.github.io/spec/2.5.1/Core-Data.xml>

Following our discussion in the introductory part of this section, what is needed for (usefully) free flow of information in the social networks of today is open standardisation both in data and in the way the services of the various networks interact. Wide application and acceptance of those will lead correspondingly to technical and semantic interoperability among the social media silos of today.

3.2 A PERSPECTIVE FOR TECHNICAL INTEROPERABILITY

The various social media platforms provide communication and other functionalities via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). This encourages developers to create applications based on their services. The various platforms try to compromise between two opposing strategic goals: serving the needs of users and developers on one hand and holding on to their existing communities on the other. It is the latter goal that goes against openness and interoperability. An initial appraisal of the offered APIs and their corresponding functionality was made by the FP7 project PADGETS⁷⁹ in a detailed analysis of the publicly available APIs for the 10 most popular social media platforms of 2010. Although there have been changes since, the basic conclusions are still valid and support the above view.

Following the above source, the APIs offered by the various platforms deal with content, such as text, images, videos or more complex forms of media such as “events”, “albums” etc. Many APIs are dedicated to the creation, (or uploading), modification, deletion and direct retrieval of specific content. Other functionalities on offer allow collection of data about any platform-specific content, such as “user ratings”, “unique visits” or retransmission to other nodes of a social network. Information retrieval on the users of the network is supported by APIs that focus on authentication and other user data.

Additional supported facilities can include individual microapplications (widgets) within a specific platform. These differ extensively but the purpose is to allow developers to have automatic access to some content and to create embedded applications to their web sites. A quick appraisal of the basic uses of the APIs offered by major platforms today is given below:⁸⁰

- Google Plus APIs. Using the Google Plus relevance graph and integrating the social media API using the Google +1 button to posts offers author more value to the search engine and helps gain better search ranking on the Google search results page.
- LinkedIn APIs. Using the LinkedIn APIs, one can build own talent graphs to increase his/her network of social connections. The LinkedIn APIs allow collection of relevant information from people with similar expertise.
- Facebook social APIs. Facebook has the largest number of social community members and this increases the value of its APIs. Using the Facebook “Like” button one can integrate powerful social signals to another web page and at the same time view what receives the highest number of likes. The use of the button averages 2.7 billion times a day.

⁷⁹ Charalabidis Y., Loukis E., Kleinfeld R, Triantafyllou A., Spinelli D., Kryvossides N., Deliverable 1.2, “Standards, Interfaces and APIs for interplatform communication in Web2.0 Social Media”, June 2010, <http://www.padgets.eu/Downloads/Deliverables.aspx>

⁸⁰ Bowden J, “Social Media APIs and Data Collection Strategies”, Business 2 Community, 20th May 2014, <http://www.business2community.com/social-media/social-media-apis-data-collection-strategies-0887426>

- Twitter APIs. Its API powered applications can track down the most popular tweets out of around 140 thousand tweets generated per day. Functionalities on offer are numerous, for example one can pull out the tweets with the highest number of re-tweets.
- YouTube APIs. Using those one can extract relevant videos and also track down which video presentations are used according to particular features.
- Pinterest graphic APIs. They allow easy categorisation of pinboards and extraction of relevant information on the latest infographics used. Various functionalities allow for example to know which pins have the highest number of re-pins within the social media community.

Many of these features can prove useful during a crisis; for example noting increased numbers of re-tweets with a similar theme can provide insight on the development and the severity of a situation long before official announcements. What however is the case today is that we face individually tailored ways of interacting with the services of major platforms: each of them presents a different API set for interaction and a massive address to all platforms or equivalently a massive retrieval of information from all platforms would require the deployment of a matching number of individual software applications. In another fashion, individual APIs from the various platforms could be mapped onto a common abstract API and this, in turn, be utilised to “push” or “pull” the relevant information in the social discourse. The latter approach was actually followed by the PADGETS platform to create a policy public address and feedback collection system (campaign system) via social media. All messages were mapped to Activity Stream messages via software modules called “Social Connectors”; their mission was to translate social media dependent API functions to one abstract publishing API and the reverse.⁸¹ In this way, potential users of the campaign node were independent from social media specific capabilities and data exchange formats.

One can imagine the potential benefits of such systems when it comes to addressing and retrieving information (messages) to/from social media during a crisis. Although there is no doubt that this adds a degree of interoperability among media platforms, this is still far from the ideal: unless each platform has acquired its own “social connector” (in the terminology of PADGETS), universal addressing is not possible and neither is universal retrieval of a specific dataset. In addition, once a platform’s APIs change or is “updated”, and this is quite a common phenomenon, interoperability is potentially lost.

3.2.1 Social media aggregation

Another form of limited interoperability is the so-called social media aggregation. This is a process of collecting content from multiple such services into a unified presentation, performed by a social network aggregator application or platform. These platforms allow network members to share their network activities with other major platforms and content appears in real time to other members who subscribe to a particular community. Using the APIs of each social network, a user is prompted to give an id/password based permission to the social-aggregation platform regarding the social media to be included. A list of the most popular aggregation platforms in use today is shown below:⁸²

⁸¹ Alvertis I., Petychakis M., Gionis G., Kleinfeld R., “A platform for managing campaigns over Social Media”, W3C/PrimeLife Federated Social Web Europe Conference, 2011, <http://www.padgets.eu/Downloads/Publications.aspx>

⁸² Ismail K., “10 Effective Tools to Aggregate All Your Social Media Updates”, Technorms, 21st August 2013, <http://www.technorms.com/33240/tools-to-aggregate-social-media-updates>

- **Flavors.me**⁸³ – One of the most popular platforms around. Users can sign up and create individual displays of favourite social media feeds and alerts, with 31 different networks under different layouts and fonts.
- **Mention.net**⁸⁴ – It allows to follow almost any social media, blog or news feed, in over 42 different languages. Users can build “teams” to share updates and content with others across a number of desktop and mobile devices, such as Apple, Microsoft and even Linux.
- **Rebel Mouse**⁸⁵ – A widely respected social aggregating system which organises updates of social networking into a manageable page viewable via a desktop or mobile device. The platform is aimed at brands, bloggers, publishers and mere individuals.
- **Cyfe**⁸⁶ – It offers an all-in-one business dashboard capable of monitoring social media updates, statistics, shares, historical data, and so forth.
- **Ming.ly**⁸⁷ – It focuses on notifying about important dates and events surrounding people and friends.
- **Postano**⁸⁸ – A platform to present social media feeds on websites or blogs in a professional way. It helps stream and control feeds live to all types of media, such as websites, mobile applications or even public digital screens.
- **Stackla**⁸⁹ – It brings popular social content and RSS feeds into one place for editing and control. It offers a powerful administration panel using word filters, flagging options and others.
- **Alternion**⁹⁰ – It can unite more than 220 social networks, along with Hotmail, Gmail, AOL, Yahoo! and more. An online address book can also be compiled.
- **Jyst.us**⁹¹ – A social aggregating system focused on simplicity for non-professionals. One can log in immediately via Facebook or Twitter and begin adding feeds to a personal Jyst webpage.
- **HootSuite**⁹² – A widely popular social network management tool which can aggregate social media feeds, with team messaging, analytics and more. It allows moderation and monitoring of incoming mentions and shares, internal talk with other team members and organisation of mass social marketing campaigns, for use via a desktop or mobile device.

Aggregation platforms can play a useful role in crisis management. They offer various ways of collecting content from a large selection of social networks, and can function as “... a central destination for social media updates”, inclusive of those of “other government services and media outlets assisting in the relief effort ...”⁹³

Example: use of a social network aggregator (Stackla⁸⁹) in crisis⁹⁴

⁸³ <http://flavors.me/>

⁸⁴ <http://mention.net/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.rebelmouse.com/>

⁸⁶ <http://www.cyfe.com/>

⁸⁷ <https://ming.ly/>

⁸⁸ <http://www.postano.com/>

⁸⁹ <http://stackla.com/>

⁹⁰ <http://www.alternion.com/>

⁹¹ <http://jyst.us/>

⁹² <https://hootsuite.com/>

⁹³ “Brisbane City Council: Cool in a Crisis”, Case Studies of Stackla, January 2013,

<http://stackla.com/project/brisbane-city-council-cool-in-a-crisis>

⁹⁴ Ibid.

“... The recent flood crisis in Brisbane, Australia found residents quickly turning to social media to consume and distribute information as the natural disaster unfolded. Furthermore, many government and community organisations used various social platforms to get their message out about warnings, closures and relief efforts.”

“... the Brisbane City Council social media team played a key role in distributing important information to its residents, and social media was a key channel.”

“... Stackla became a central destination⁹⁵ for not only their own social media updates, but those of other government services and media outlets assisting in the relief effort. The result was a hub for all information being distributed by official bodies – Fire Brigade, Council, Police, State Emergency Service and local media. And by using Stackla’s unique moderation and publishing tools, all information published was authentic, relevant and from a credible source. Also, it became the perfect tool for internal monitoring purposes, with team directing councillors and other key staff to Stackla to keep abreast of social media activity around the event.”

“... Additionally, Stackla became an excellent source of [user-generated images](#) from around the city, providing a live user-generated image stream as the event unfolded. And Stackla’s usefulness wasn’t over there, with the social media team creating a Facebook app that collected information from a range of social media and traditional sources ...”

“... Technology application summary:

- Central destination for ‘official’ flood information for media and residents
- Internal monitoring tool for key stakeholders
- Facility to create a Facebook app to highlight information coming from other social media sources such as Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and RSS Live photo stream
- Sharing & commenting platform ...”

3.2.2 A vision

Having examined partial solutions for technical interoperability, the question that comes to mind is what we can expect a world of truly interoperable social networks to be like. A good visionary answer is provided by the schematic diagramme of D. Hinchcliffe shown below. The basic features describe a future Social Media Transfer Protocol (SMTP), deliberately named in this way so as to stress the similarities and analogies with the usual e-mail SMTP standard:⁹⁶

A Social Media Transfer Protocol:

- **Universal social media address.** This amounts to a simple, consistent and broadly understood global address system to equip every member of every network with a uniquely identified address.
- **A “follow anyone on any social network” mechanism.** With the exception of private messages, addressing is mainly for mentioning people or replying to them in public

⁹⁵ <http://social.brisbane.qld.gov.au/>

⁹⁶ Hinchcliffe D., “Where is interoperability for social media?”, ZDNet, Enterprise Web 2.0, 28 February 2014, <http://www.zdnet.com/where-is-interoperability-for-social-media-7000026894/>

threads, with the added important property that your activity stream can show all posts from those you follow across various social networks.

- **Sharing of social metadata.** Relations to entities, such as “likes”, “retweets”, and others such as posts/status updates shared in a common way throughout all social networks.
- **Extensibility.** This is important for further evolution and innovation, but at the same time prone to introduce fragmentation as extensions may not be agreed upon and/or adopted by all at the same time.
- **Business model support.** “To be blunt, without something to preserve the interests of the large services, there will never be a successful social media interoperability standard. What this looks like is also one of *the* hardest issues to resolve, but it's also the linchpin in my opinion to making any interoperability standard a success.”⁹⁷

Figure 2. A Social Media Transfer Protocol functional vision⁹⁸

3.3 A PERSPECTIVE FOR SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY

As is well-known, solutions to the problems of semantic interoperability are complex and encompass many aspects of Information Technology including deep theoretical concerns. Semantic interoperability lies in the heart of the goal of achieving information integration across heterogeneous datasets; this, in turn, implies ontology integration and this, again, needs a rigorous foundation not tied to any specific representational or logical formalism⁹⁹, something not yet available on a commonly agreed basis. What appears to be a tangible goal is utilising partial solutions based on specific domain ontologies which offer both a semantic anchor and a more rigorous vocabulary of standardised terminology. A variety of such

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Goguen J., “Three perspectives on Information Integration”, Dagstuhl Seminar Proceedings 04391 on Semantic Interoperability and Integration, 2005, <http://drops.dagstuhl.de/opus/volltexte/2005/38/>

solutions for social media (FOAF, SIOC and SocIoS) were examined in COSMIC Deliverable D3.2.1.¹⁰⁰

Along these lines, the semantic issues facing the informational needs of crisis response regarding semantic interoperability and integration can be partially answered by adopting standard terminologies for crises and response activities shared by all responders and the public, who may participate through social networks, possibly utilising compliant specialist applications. The concept is not new, various researchers and practitioners¹⁰¹ have stressed the need to develop open standards so as to advance interoperability in crisis management. The variety of application specific ontologies, which have been developed for crisis information management to aid interoperability in specific scenarios, has been reviewed by Liu et al¹⁰² under the criteria of subject area coverage, design and current use, and conformance to standards. The following table shows the most relevant and comprehensive (from the point of view of crisis management) crisis ontologies, their aim and the concepts they represent.

Table 4. Relevant crisis ontologies, aims and concepts they represent¹⁰³

Representative Crisis Ontologies	Types of Crisis Management Systems aimed for	Requirements of Information Representation
SOKNOS	Information integration for resource planning	Categorisation of damages and resources, deploy regulations defining the relations between them
SIADEx	Planning under uncertainty for decision support	Taxonomy of resources, legal information on the use of resources, operational targets and tasks for specific crisis scenarios, representation of uncertainty (temporal, resource and location)
ISyCri	Crisis response coordination	Categories of entities affected by crises, the treatment system, the crisis description
MOAC, HXL	Humanitarian disaster response and relief	Classification of damages, crises, response activities and resources; geo location about displaced persons
WB-OS	Web sites for disaster management	Features, components and information used to create disaster management web sites

The authors' research showed that the 11 critical subject areas they identified as covering the information concepts needed for crisis management were represented existing ontologies and that 65% of them were semantically interoperable.

In response to the above findings, researchers of Project Disaster 2.0¹⁰⁴ (within whose frame the above review of existing ontologies was also made) created a formal ontology in the aim to cover the identified key interoperability gaps of existing ontologies. The result was the DiRes, an ontology for describing emergency and disaster events, and the key factors associated with disaster response activities¹⁰⁵. DiRes defines terms relating to disasters (what

¹⁰⁰ I. Kotsiopoulos, A. Yannopoulos, H. Watson, R. Finn, K. Wadhwa, A. Papadimitriou, "Political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies", Deliverable 3.2.1, COSMIC, October 2013

¹⁰¹ Di Maio, P, "An open ontology for open source emergency response systems", 2008, <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.93.1829>

¹⁰² Liu S., Brewster C., Shaw D., "Ontologies for Crisis Management: A Review of State of the Art in Ontology Design and Usability", Proceedings of the 10th International ISCRAM Conference – Baden-Baden, Germany, May 2013, T. Comes, F. Fiedrich, S. Fortier, J. Geldermann and L. Yang, eds.

¹⁰³ Ibid., Table 2

¹⁰⁴ Disaster 2.0 Project, EC Directorate-General Home Affairs, HOME/2010/CIPS/AG/002, <http://www.disaster20.eu>

¹⁰⁵ Ibid., <http://www.disaster20.eu/dires>

has happened), operations (what can be done), people and organisation (who are involved and take actions), resources (what are needed and used), time and location (when and where), and the damage that a disaster has caused. DiRes specialises the Friend of a Friend (FOAF) ontology¹⁰⁶, the W3C Organisation ontology¹⁰⁷ and the Open Geospatial Consortium GeoSPARQL ontology¹⁰⁸ in order to describe correspondingly people from different governmental agencies and organisations, the origin place and boundary of a disaster event, and the check-in location of a disaster response operation by first responders and aid agencies.

The specification of DiRes is still evolving and its wider acceptance is dependent on a variety of factors ranging from policy (for example the fragmentation observed in the EU) to ease of use and to added adoption by governmental and non-governmental organisations.

3.4 A POLICY ISSUE IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Dr Axel Bruns explores the role of Twitter in disseminating information in the aftermath of the Queensland floods in Australia, as an example of the capabilities of social networks in crises¹⁰⁹:

A policy issue in crisis management

“...What would be much more valuable would be an approach which could enable a frictionless crowd-sourcing process – the automatic detection, aggregation, and evaluation of tweets that may point to a genuine emergency...”

“...However, what’s holding back the development of a Twitter-based crisis detector network is not so much the technology, but Twitter’s increasingly restrictive policy of granting access to its data, even for researchers working in the public interest. It is technically possible for us to check the public message streams of Australia’s estimated two million Twitter accounts for any weak signals of emerging crises, however, the cost of doing so is too great...”

“...we must find a way to scale up – by persuading Twitter to moderate its data monetisation stance, at least in the context of projects which demonstrably benefit the common good...”

Here we have an interesting data sharing issue. Twitter is asked to share collective historical data for the benefit of crisis detection. This, however, and according to the legislative framework of the locality of the processors of such data, may conflict with personal data protection laws and regulations.

3.5 CONCLUSIONS

Social media are somehow a victim of their success. Large private platforms have realised the value of controlling information and restricting the once open flow of the Internet. This so called “walled gardens” situation has had profound effects in limiting acceptance of open

¹⁰⁶ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec>

¹⁰⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org>

¹⁰⁸ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/geosparql>

¹⁰⁹ Bruns A., “At times of crisis Twitter shines brightest”, CONTINUITY, 3rd Quarter 2012, <http://snurb.info/files/2012/Continuity.pdf>

standards and, in turn, limiting interoperability among the various platforms. The result is that proposed open standards such as OpenSocial and Activity Streams have not gained widespread acceptance and true technical interoperability (in the sense of being able to address everybody within the social fabric, share social metadata and have a controlled way to accommodate protocol extensions and updates) is still absent. Correspondingly, semantic interoperability, an even more difficult issue, is at an even less developed state.

Any advance in interoperability would be good news for crisis management. Addressing everybody and retrieving information from any platform is a valuable asset during a crisis. The interesting development here is some advances on the semantic front. As crises have a relatively limited vocabulary, concepts and their inter-relations can be formalised as crisis ontologies and then utilised by possibly specific social media applications. In this respect, we have a variety of crisis specific ontologies already in use, including the DiRes ontology by the European project Disaster 2.0.

Partial solutions for interaction – but not full interoperability – among the services offered by social media platforms are in use today via the Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) of those platforms. Although they differ according from network to network, they offer content and user-related functionality and also microapplications (widgets). These features can prove useful during a crisis; for example noting increased numbers of re-tweets with a similar theme can provide insight on the development and the severity of a situation long before official announcements. Another by-product of the platforms' APIs is social media aggregation, a process of collecting content from multiple services into a unified presentation. An extensive number of network aggregator applications exist today, and a role for them in crisis management has already been established. As the experience with the floods in Brisbane (2013) showed, aggregation platforms offer various ways of collecting content from a large selection of social networks, and can function as a central destination for social media updates originating from all sorts of rescue organisations.

Finally, one should not overlook the policy issues related to opening up social media data: personal data may be involved and the relevant legislation – which also differs among countries – may place its own limitations, despite the existence of cases where there are obvious benefits to crisis management.

4 EMERGENCY RESPONSE SCENARIOS

The study of the FOCUS project¹¹⁰ on natural disasters' management in the EU, observes that there is a lack of a systematic approach on the security of citizens at EU level. It also notes that “research is diffused and often of bad quality as it is not based on real data and basic practices: literal essays made for the officials usually do not solve the problems. Sources for research in the field are diffused among European, state and regional levels and also between public and private participating parties.” Moreover, the FOCUS researchers state that for the majority of natural disasters in the EU there are no systematic measures aimed at preparedness for naturally occurring crises and neither is there a systematic tool for recovery after such disasters. The European Solidarity Fund is characterised as a partial measure which can only help countries affected by large scale (above a certain threshold) disasters.

FOCUS recommends that the solutions proposed by professional researchers should be reviewed and should lead to practical implementations. Researchers state that although there are hundreds of projects which at various levels (technical, social, organisational) address natural disasters, a synthesis of the individual results into a single concept is currently missing.

Although improvements are evident, for example the European Civil Protection exercises¹¹¹ such as the EU-Taranis 2013¹¹², the lack of a systematic approach noted above means that there are no general EU-wide guidelines and preparedness plans publicly disseminated and available to guide stakeholders and actors involved in the crisis chain of events. In addition, the scenarios of the exercises conducted under the auspices of the Community Mechanism for Civil Protection¹¹³ are not generally available, as evidenced in the published list of the European Civil Protection exercises¹¹⁴.

4.1 BASIC CONSTITUENTS

According to the Oxford dictionaries¹¹⁵ a scenario is “a postulated sequence or development of events” and/or “a setting, in particular for a work of art or literature”. Transferring this to serve our purpose, a crisis management scenario should include both aspects of the definition, i.e. a setting within which action (events) take place as well as a sequential presentation of the events constituting such action. Another feature of such a scenario is the interaction between external events (i.e. the natural course of a disaster such as a wildfire or a flood) and the response of the safety and security actors involved. These actors are formal bodies implicated in the management (mitigation) of the effects of a crisis at all levels, i.e. at preparation,

¹¹⁰ Disaster management in the EU – Present and future: Challenges for research, Foresight Security Scenarios – Mapping Research to a Comprehensive Approach to Exogenous EU Roles (FOCUS), July 2012, <http://www.focusproject.eu/documents/14976/5d763378-1198-4dc9-86ff-c46959712f8a>

¹¹¹ European Commission: Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection exercises 2002-2013, http://ec.europa.eu/echo/civil_protection/civil/prote/exercises.htm

¹¹² EU-Taranis 2013 exercise, <http://www.taranis2013.eu/en/zur-ubung>. In fact, the exercise would be an excellent opportunity for disseminating the results as well as the scenarios assumed and tested to a wider audience, but unfortunately these are not available.

¹¹³ European Mechanism of Civil Protection, http://ec.europa.eu/echo/policies/disaster_response/mechanism_en.htm

¹¹⁴ European Commission: Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection exercises 2002-2013, http://ec.europa.eu/echo/civil_protection/civil/prote/exercises.htm

¹¹⁵ Oxford Dictionaries at <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/scenario> by the Oxford University Press

warning, response and recovery. They are organisations mandated by the appropriate authorities, be them salaried professionals (state or hired private organisations) or volunteers (such as citizens' organisations and civil society organisations¹¹⁶).

The common characteristic of both of these categories is the existence of some structure under which they operate, which usually includes the mandate, the hierarchy and a way of action prescribed according to a taxonomy of conditions. This structure is collectively referred to under the term “Standard Operating Procedures” (SOPs)¹¹⁷ and plays an important part in shaping the effectiveness of the response to a crisis. In the words of the US Environmental Protection Agency¹¹⁸:

- “SOPs detail the regularly recurring work processes that are to be conducted or followed within an organisation. They document the way activities are to be performed to facilitate consistent conformance to technical and quality system requirements and to support data quality. They may describe, for example, fundamental programmatic actions and technical actions such as analytical processes, and processes for maintaining, calibrating, and using equipment. SOPs are intended to be specific to the organisation or facility whose activities are described and assist that organisation to maintain their quality control and quality assurance processes and ensure compliance with governmental regulations.”

A typical general structure of such a procedure and its constituent parts is shown below.

Figure 3. General structure of a Standard Operating Procedure¹¹⁹

A scenario, therefore, of any crisis should take into account the operational environment of the responders, which is shaped by their applicable standard operating procedures, which, in turn, characterise the organisation and reflect its mandate. As mentioned before, organisations

¹¹⁶ These are also frequently called “Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

¹¹⁷ Although the US military use the term “Standing Operating Procedures” to stress the fact that these are unique to a certain organisation and not universal.

¹¹⁸ United States Environmental Protection Agency, “Guidance for Preparing Standard Operating Procedures, EPA QA/G-6”, April 2007, <http://www.epa.gov/quality/qs-docs/g6-final.pdf>

¹¹⁹ Weeden Marcia, “The Well Written SOP – Critical for Continuous Improvement”, Writing Assistants Inc, <http://www.writingassist.com/resources/articles/the-well-written-sop-critical-for-continuous-improvement>

at European level do not publicise such information; in contrast, there is extensive data published by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) in the US, which is indicative of the way responders to a crisis should react.

The basic elements of a scenario for response to a catastrophic incident will have to cope with cascading events and will necessitate challenging legal, policy, and regulatory interventions. Standard operating procedures of large organisations in charge of emergency response are indicative of typical response scenarios. In what follows, we show such a generic scenario derived from the corresponding FEMA documentation¹²⁰. The words in brackets and in italics show the correspondence of these stages the criteria to be addressed of Figure 1 of section 2.5.

Planning (*preparation*)

This is the stage where the response mission and objectives are set, and tasks for action are defined. It is of interest to note here that the FEMA recommends that at this early stage “a systematic process engaging the whole community as appropriate in the development of executable strategic, operational, and/or community-based approaches to meet defined objectives” is undertaken. This is the first manifestation of a one-way communication between the responder and the public and, of course, includes social media.

Public Information and Warning (*warning and response*)

This stage comes as a realisation of the community engagement plan of the previous stage and lasts throughout the crisis incident. It includes information on threats or hazards, action taken and the available assistance. The FEMA recommends “clear, consistent, accessible, and culturally and linguistically appropriate methods to effectively relay” critical information concerning life-sustaining actions.

Operational Coordination (*response*)

This concerns all critical stakeholders and core capabilities for SOP-compliant command, control and coordination structures for response

Critical Transportation (*response*)

Provision of transportation at all levels, such as the creation of safe transportation corridors for evacuees, survivors, and subsequent restoration of basic services.

Environmental Response/Health and Safety (*response and recovery*)

Concerns health and safety hazard assessments, issue of guidance for personnel, if needed, prescribes action for response personnel and provides adequate resources for response and later recovery.

Fatality Management Services (*response and recovery*)

This includes body recovery, victim identification, temporary mortuary solutions, sharing of information with mass care services for reunifying family members and caregivers and the provision of counselling.

Infrastructure Systems (*response and recovery*)

This includes the maintenance and stabilisation of all critical infrastructure functions supporting life, community and rescue operations.

¹²⁰ FEMA, “National Preparedness Goal”, 1st Edition, 2011, http://www.fema.gov/media-library-data/20130726-1828-25045-9470/national_preparedness_goal_2011.pdf

Mass Care Services (*response and recovery*)

Provision of life-sustaining services such as hydration, feeding and sheltering to affected populations.

Mass Search and Rescue Operations (*response*)

The goal is saving the greatest number of endangered lives in the shortest time possible. The important for COSMIC feature here is the FEMA recommendation for community-based search and rescue support operations across a wide geographically dispersed area. Here social media can mobilise the community into locating possible survivors and persons in need.

On-scene Security and Protection (*response*)

This aspect concerns the creation of a safe, secure and lawful environment affected communities and responders.

Operational Communications (*response*)

This step concerns the availability of communication capacity, both among response organisations and their members as well as among communities and communities-responders.

Public and Private Services and Resources (*response and recovery*)

It involves provision of essential public and private services and resources to the affected population and the surrounding communities, for example emergency power, fuel, food, healthcare, fire-fighting and others.

Public Health and Medical Services (*response and recovery*)

This step concerns lifesaving medical treatment and countermeasures to combat additional diseases and injuries.

Situational Assessment (*warning and response*)

This includes all decision-relevant information on the hazard, the cascading effects and the status of the response. What is interesting for COSMIC here is the FEMA recommendation that “governmental, private and civic sector resources within and outside of the affected area” are used for this purpose. As will be seen in their Standard Operating Procedures for communication, a significant part of this is attributed to social media.

4.2 SOCIAL MEDIA: ROLE AND PRESENCE

The role of social media in the basic scenario described above is two fold: covering communication needs including information sharing and help in building situational awareness. In what follows we elaborate on the role of social media from the point of view of standard operating procedures (SOPs) as described by the FEMA¹²¹. Annex R of the procedures¹²² refers explicitly to digital and social media and to web-based and other interactive communication with the public. The accepted concept is that “official websites, blogs, photos, videos, social media sites, text messages (SMS), and smartphone applications are effective tools to advise and inform the public if used in a coordinated, strategic, and

¹²¹ “Emergency Support Function 15 (External Affairs): Homeland Security, Standard Operating Procedures”, FEMA, August 2013, http://www.fema.gov/media-library-data/965d87d8c5ffc4bccb01979913e01fc/ESF15_SOP_08-30-2013-02.pdf

¹²² Ibid.

timely manner, and should be used in concert with other non-digital communication channels.”

The background setting of the social media presence according to the FEMA is shown in the following table. Of particular interest is the recognition of the role of social media in health incidents, where they are seen as the fastest means of public announcement.

Table 5. The operating background of the FEMA SOPs (article 4.2) on communication with the public (outreach)¹²³

<p>4.2 Strategic Communications Assumptions (one-way communication and information sharing¹²⁴)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>The first public announcement of a potential public health or medical emergency will come through social media, followed by announcements in traditional news media.</i> 2. <i>The public affected by the incident will need to be informed quickly about the measures they can take to protect their health and the health of their families. Regardless of the type of incident, people will be concerned about real or perceived health impacts and will raise questions about protecting health.</i> 3. <i>There will be incomplete information, misinformation, rumors, and misconceptions among the public.</i> 4. <i>There will be an insatiable demand for information from the public and from domestic and international media.</i> 5. <i>There will be overwhelming public pressure on government to provide facts quickly.</i>

Another important aspect in these procedures is the provision of article 2.2 which states that “all content, messaging, and communication channels should be accessible to populations with access and functional needs and populations with limited English proficiency”, the process being coordinated by the Digital Communications Specialist of the Media Relations Unit of the Joint Information Center (JIC).

The main information portal is USA.gov, operated by the General Services Administration (GSA), supplemented by departmental and agency websites and their corresponding social media sites. In fact the procedure states that “agencies should always use pre-established accounts during an incident because the account already has an established base of users and level of trust with social media users.”

Specific guidelines are included for keeping messages up to date, responding to questions from users, cross-linking with sites of other agencies and keeping content readable in an accessible format.

Finally, article 5.0 refers explicitly to “Social Media Monitoring and Reporting for Situational Awareness”. In fact monitoring publicly available content across online channels is considered as being “as important as posting information”. The Emergency Support Function 15 of the SOPs is explicitly instructed to “use publicly available social media sites for situational awareness” and to “search on appropriate keywords, hash-tags, and other search terms on digital channels to find information for situational awareness.” The actor charged with such functions, i.e. the Digital Communications Specialist “should monitor for messages sent from the public directly to the agency social media accounts” and take action in cases where incorrect information is discovered.

A case study scenario on Hurricane Sandy of 2012 where more than 15 staff from multiple FEMA offices at the peak of the storm were supporting the social media operation, via social media content and managing media accounts such as the newly established Facebook and Twitter accounts to provide updates on Sandy response and recovery. Situational awareness

¹²³ Ibid..

¹²⁴ In the terminology of [Figure 1: Scenario criteria](#) of section 2.5.

was also aided by shared “social media discussions on power outages, volunteering and donations, and sentiment about the response efforts.” An important feature of the operation was rumour control, described in the following table.

Table 6. Rumour control measures during Hurricane Sandy¹²⁵

Hurricane Sandy Rumor Control

- ◆ □A page on *fema.gov* and *m.fema.gov* (FEMA’s mobile site) was created. When a rumor was identified, the social media team worked with ESF #15 staff to track down additional information and gather the correct information. These details were then added to the Rumor Control page, providing clear language about the misinformation and resources where people could find correct information for each rumor.
- ◆ □Rumor Control messages were shared widely by FEMA’s social media accounts, as well as by other responding agencies. The social media team shared this information with the interagency through the NICCL, and collaborated with state and local partners to share these messages and expand their reach.

Recapitulating, the above paragraphs show that social media have established a firm role in crisis management and have become part of the standard operating procedures of a large organisation such as the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). As COSMIC research has shown so far, their contribution has been tried and tested in recent disasters and crises and there is no reason for this to be missing from the established procedures of European organisations of a similar mission, for example the European Mechanism for Civil Protection.

4.3 REAL-LIFE RESCUE-MISSION SCENARIOS – THE CASE OF AN NGO

Following the general concepts from the point of view of standard operating procedures which stem from a large state organisation, as shown in the previous sections, we now turn to response scenarios concerning responders and responders and the public, realised by another type of stakeholder, namely a civil society organisation (NGO). These are based on real-life experiences of our partner organisation Hellenic Rescue Team (HRT). Before those, we refer briefly to the organisational structure and the standard operating procedures used by HRT for the activation of the response mechanism.

4.3.1 Organisational structure

The Hellenic Rescue Team is a Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) dedicated to Search And Rescue (SAR), whose members have participated in SAR operations since 1978 on a voluntary basis. Since 1994, HRT has operated in the legal form of an association. The central administration is based in Thessaloniki, with over 30 branch offices throughout Greece.

The organisation has been certified by the General Secretariat of Civil Protection¹²⁶, belonging to the Hellenic Ministry of the Interior under Registration No. six (6), and since June 2005 by the UN’s International Search And Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG)¹²⁷. HRT is in constant cooperation with the Hellenic Foreign Ministry and the European Community Humanitarian Office (ECHO)¹²⁸. It is also a full member of the International

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Hellenic Organisation for Civil Protection, <http://www.civilprotection.gr>

¹²⁷ International Search and Rescue Advisory Group, INSARAG Secretariat, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), UN, <http://www.insarag.org>

¹²⁸ EU Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection department (ECHO), http://ec.europa.eu/echo/about/index_en.htm

Maritime Rescue Federation (IMRF)¹²⁹, the World Mountain Rescue Federation (IKAR-CISA)¹³⁰, and the International Rescue dog Association (IRO)¹³¹.

With a workforce of more than 2000 volunteers throughout Greece, HRT participates and has participated in search and rescue operations in emergency situations and massive disasters throughout the world. Staff includes volunteer professional and amateur rescuers with sound scientific and technical training. The organisation chart is shown in the next picture. The organisation is represented by a person who presides over the Board of Directors (President).

Figure 4. Organisation chart of the Hellenic Rescue Team

4.3.2 Activation procedure of the response mechanism in crisis situations abroad

In what follows, we first show the corresponding standard operating procedures of HRT prior to their application in realistic scenarios.

On receipt of initial information relating to a possible disaster, the management of operations is activated and the following procedure is initialised:

PHASE A: (Building initial situation awareness for organising response¹³²)

1. The Operations Division carries out an initial cross reference of the received information (signal). This procedure is executed using all possible communication channels

¹²⁹ <http://www.international-maritime-rescue.org/>

¹³⁰ IKAR CISA - International Commission for Alpine Rescue Commission - Internationale du Sauvetage Alpin
<http://www.ikar-cisa.org/>

¹³¹ <http://www.iro-dogs.org/en/iro-home/introduction.html>

¹³² In the terminology of Figure 1: Scenario criteria of section 2.5.

(GDACS¹³³, the On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (OSOCC), traditional and **social media** and others)

- if the signal is not verified then the procedure is repeated in two hours time.
 - if the signal is verified then:
2. The Mission Support Team (MST) is initialised and the Board of Directors is informed of the situation.
 3. The MST
 - Monitors the Virtual On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (VOSOCC)¹³⁴, the GDACS, and all media and issues brief & concise reports for internal briefings.
 - Proceeds to send requests for sponsorship for a possible mission in cooperation with the Office of Press & Public Relations.
 - Informs all divisions and branches for the possible initialisation of a mission in the affected country.

Instructions – notes

- In PHASE A an initial assessment of the situation is carried out on the basis of the first information collected. In order to save time in case an operation to the affected country is decided, the steps required to prepare for such an operation are planned even before a decision is made.
- All the information collected by the team's monitoring mechanism has as a final addressee the Director of Operations, who is in constant communication with the Board of Directors to support the decision-making process.
- The Mission Support Team comes under the Division of Operations.
- Steps 1 - 3 must be completed within 6 hours from the receipt of the initial signal (T+6h).
- In T+6h the first assessment of the situation should be completed and a response decision finalised.

PHASE B – Finding financial resources – How to dispatch (*Communication among responders and law enforcement agencies*)¹³⁵

Phase B is conducted once the first assessment of the situation has been considered as positive and a decision on the necessity of response has been taken.

1. The Division of Operations prepares the initial budget of the mission and submits it to the Board of Directors.
2. The Board of Directors (BoD) considers possible means of funding (self-funded or through sponsorships) with potential sponsors already contacted in Phase A.
3. Depending on various factors, such as the type of emergency, the location of the country where the emergency has occurred, and others, the BoD considers sending an initial Exploratory Team (ET) of only 2-3 people to the affected area to assess the situation from first hand and to provide inside information on the situation.
4. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs is contacted by the President of HRT for the possible disposal of a C-130 aircraft in order to transport the team to the emergency site.
5. If the funds are available then a final decision is made to launch a response mission.

¹³³ The Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (GDACS) is a cooperation framework between the United Nations, the European Commission and disaster managers worldwide to improve alerts, information exchange and coordination in the first phase after major sudden-onset disasters.

<http://www.gdacs.org/monitor.aspx>

¹³⁴ This is part of the GDACS for information exchange and coordination of bilateral assistance in the early phase after major disasters, <http://vosocc.unocha.org>

¹³⁵ In the terminology of [Figure 1: Scenario criteria](#) of section 2.5.

Instructions – Notes

- Financing of an operation can be self-financed or through sponsorships. Self-financed operations usually only occur for nearby incidents.
- The information that is considered when assessing the situation includes, among others, the number of victims and the status of any international mobilisation.
- The Exploratory Team (ET) consists of individuals experienced in missions and similar procedures, regardless of specialty or department.
- The departure of an Task Force (following the ET) should occur within 18 hours of receiving the initial signal (T+18h) and only once the final decision for the operation becomes positive.

The following actions occur simultaneously (*Response*¹³⁶)

1. The MST performs preparatory tasks for the mission of the ET, which departs as soon as they are finished. These tasks include the following:
 - Collecting information on accessing the affected area (point of entry).
 - Compiling a contact list of local bodies.
 - Reporting to the VOSOCC.
 - Briefing the ET on the latest development (situation reports).
 - Means of transportation, tickets, etc.
2. The team prepares for the mission by retesting the equipment and notifying members for the creation of a task force. This task force is established with a written joint decision of all branches and divisions which will participate in the operation as well as the Board of Directors.
3. Confirmation must be obtained on the logistics of the operation, i.e. when the team departs, how, etc.
4. The ET departs within a time interval which should be not larger than 24 hours after the receipt of the initial signal (T+24h)

PHASE C – Mission in progress (*Response*¹³⁷)

The following Operations Support Procedures are applicable during an operation by the Division of Operations:

1. Activate the HRT's 24-hour central Operations Centre (OC). Personnel are provided by all divisions who can support the mission.
2. Regional operation centres are also activated so as to support the OC by collecting information on all the latest developments via the monitoring of all prescribed frequency and communication channels.
3. The Press Office periodically issues press releases on the status of operations. The material is supplied by the Division of Operations. Updates on the operations are also posted on the HRT's website and social media accounts, such as those in Facebook, Twitter, YouTube.
4. A complete and detailed log book on all OC actions relating to matters concerning the evolution of the mission, must be constantly maintained.

Instructions – Notes

Once the ET arrives at its destination, i.e. the affected area, it acts according to the INSARAG guidelines, as briefly shown below:

¹³⁶ In the terminology of Figure 1: Scenario criteria of section 2.5.

¹³⁷ Ibid.

- Contact the Reception / Departure Centre (RDC);
- Login to OSOCC to retrieve and post information on the current situation;
- Set up a Base Of Operations (BOO) camp. Set up network communications;
- Login to the OSOCC for mission assignment;
- Participate in daily cluster meetings;
- When the mission ends, contact the RDC;
- Return home.

Every evening (local time of the affected region) the ET informs the OC with a detailed report on the actions performed throughout the day.

The OC also continuously monitors the VOSOCC so as to provide extra support to the ET.

PHASE D – Return

1. Upon arrival of the team an immediate debriefing follows
2. 1-2 weeks after the operation the debriefing of other groups and individuals is performed
3. A final report on all actions performed during the mission is drafted and sent to the OCHA within 45 days after the return.

The application of the following procedures is shown in the two earthquake incidents below.

4.3.3 Real-life scenario: Haiti 2010

In January 12th, 2010 and at about 22:00, an earthquake of magnitude 7 on the Richter scale occurred 27 miles west of the Haitian capital, Port-au-Prince. The scenario of actions is as follows, categorised according to the terminology of Figure 1: Scenario criteria of section 2.5 (underlined in italics).

Warning and Response – Information Sharing

The reception of the initial information (signal) on the incident took place at 22:30 of the same day via the platform of the GDACS (Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System). The HRT's Division of Operations activated the team's response mechanism for international crises. Cross-checks of the information received were performed by monitoring the international media and all notification and cooperation systems between the EU and the UN (GDACS and VOSOCC). Upon positive verification of the information, the Board of Directors of HRT was informed and the Mission Support Team was activated.

Response – Two-way Communication – Information Sharing

The Mission Support Team (MST) started to monitor closely the available information channels and updated in real-time the Director of Operations on all latest developments. The Press Office was also contacted for the publication of regular press releases on the current situation, while emergency information was also propagated to all members of the Hellenic Rescue Team of all sections and branches on the possibility of sending team members to the affected area. At the same time, the Office of Press and Public Relations directly contacted potential sponsors in order to investigate the possibility of covering the costs through external sponsorship.

Response – Two-way Communication – Information Sharing Among Responders and Law Enforcement Agencies

Three to four hours after receiving the first signal, the HRT had already formed a draft list of available members who declared an interest in the mission. Also, all evidence suggested an increased operational status indicating that a rescue team could be sent within the calculated timeframe.

An initial budget was soon after established by the Director of Operations and submitted to the Board of Directors for approval. An emergency meeting of the Board of Directors was conducted in the early hours of January 13th, 2010 (T + 11h) and after taking into account the latest information and the initial budget gave a negative answer for sending a team to Haiti, as the support costs of such an effort were prohibitive. This was so because almost no response had been received from prospective donors and the mission had to be self-financed. Because of the fact that at an operational level the team was ready to respond, a small exploratory team of 2 persons was established and set on a 24h alert ready to depart immediately.

The Board sent formal requests to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs for the disposal of a C-130 aircraft and the possibility of the team boarding on it. By that time the Greek Government had not yet decided whether it would officially send any help to Haiti (T+15h).

The Mission Support Team (MST) performed all procedural tasks regarding the departure of both the Exploratory Team (ET) and the Task Force (TF) while the necessary equipment was also retested to confirm their operational status. The list of available volunteers for the mission was also compiled. From the list of available volunteers that had expressed an interest for their participation in the mission, 10 members were selected to form the operational team which was approved by the Board of Directors, the involved heads of departments and the Education and Management Divisions. The ET and TF were ready to depart as soon as the means of transportation could be financed.

Over the course of time and while the volume of information about the event and its consequences kept increasing, the HRT, fully prepared for departure, began to investigate the possibility of converting the rescue mission into a humanitarian mission. Possible sponsors were contacted once again and, eventually, a sponsor who devoted considerable funds for the support the team's needs was found (T + 3d). The funds were sufficient not only to cover the cost of transportation, as the Greek State had yet to announce the dispatch of any kind of assistance, but also to fund humanitarian and development action.

Response – Situational Awareness

Upon completion of all the necessary formalities for the disbursement of the amount, airline tickets were issued for the immediate departure of a 10-member Task Force. Due to the fact that the airport of Port-au-Prince was closed and flights were only accepted if originating from official public authorities for assistance missions, the HRT's team flew to a neighbouring country, namely the Dominican Republic, and from there using its own means (charter bus) transferred to the capital of Haiti. The team had departed knowing that the equipment would follow in a cargo flight to Haiti. Eventually though, and due to problems at the airport, it was later estimated that the cargo would arrive 10 days after the HRT had reached Haiti. Since the formulated operations plan forecast the HRT to remain in Haiti for 10 to 12 days, it was mutually agreed that there was no point in sending the equipment after all. This was the point that changed the objective of the mission.

Upon arrival, the ET contacted the Reception/Departure Centre of INSARAG and was informed on the situation. They also met with a representative of UNISEF to investigate the

possibility of a development programme concerning the orphan children of Haiti. On the same day, the team set camp at the location selected by the United Nations and a network of communications was established to allow members to communicate with each other but also to allow exchange of information with the Operations Centre of the Hellenic Rescue Team in Greece.

On the 22nd of October, 2010 the United Nations officially announced that all search and rescue missions had been terminated and soon after all international SAR teams present in Haiti since the first few hours after the earthquake began preparations for departure. On the 23rd of October though, and despite the termination of all SAR missions, efforts of the HRT's ET led to the rescue of a survivor found alive in the ruins of a building.

Response – Two-way Communication – Information Sharing between Responders and the Public

With the help of French and American SAR teams, the victim was retrieved from the debris 11 days after the devastating earthquake. It is worth mentioning that **the information on a possible survivor was propagated very rapidly throughout the world via a tweet that was broadcasted at the time.** The “tip” was confirmed by the United Nations centre of operations and subsequently the SAR teams available at the site were commanded to proceed with the rescue operation.

Recovery – Two-way Communication – Information Sharing between Responders and the Public

During the remaining days, the HRT was in constant communication with the UN's coordination centre and until the 28th of January, 2011, they were asked to cross-check several other “tips” similar to the tweet that lead to the rescue of the aforementioned victim. HRT also participated in the successful recuperation and transport of electronic equipment and documents from a collapsed UN building in Haiti.

On the 27th of January 2011 HRT began preparations for the departure of the team from Haiti, which occurred on the very next day. On the 28th of January 2010, the Hellenic Rescue Team arrived at the Macedonia airport of Thessaloniki and over the course of the next days, essential processes (debriefing) were performed in order to draw conclusions and valuable lessons from the mission as well as prepare a report to be sent to the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA).

4.3.4 Real-life scenario: Chile 2010

On the 27th of February 2010 and at 08:34 Eastern European time, an earthquake of size 8.8 of the Richter scale struck Chile. The initial information on the earthquake was received from the media and was immediately cross-referenced by the available briefing channels of the Hellenic Rescue Team (GDACS, VOSOCC and social media). The Mission Support Team (MST) was immediately activated by the Division of Operations while at the same time the Board of Directors was informed of the situation.

Based on the procedure followed in such cases and with the recent experience of the Haitian earthquake in mind, the MST proceeded with the continuous monitoring and recording of all new information through GDACS, VOSOCC, traditional and social media while also publishing briefings for the event every two hours. In cooperation with the Office of Press and

Public Relations, potential sponsors to support a possible mission were contacted. All branches of the HRT were also contacted and informed with all the latest data on the incident. In less than five hours, a picture of the situation had already taken shape and the Division of Operations submitted the initial budget to the Board of Directors, which was examined taking into consideration all current data.

The sponsor who had contributed all the necessary funds for the Haiti mission again provided financial help and an Exploratory Team of two (2) individuals was formed. This would depart immediately once a more explicit picture of the situation was available and once preparatory work could be completed to support the arrival of a subsequent Task Force. The ET was ready to depart immediately for Chile within 19 hours (T+19h) of the reception of the initial signal. At the same time, procedures for the formation of a Task Force continued, including retesting of the equipment (even though it had been proven operational during the previous mission in Haiti). Upon arrival in Chile the ET contacted local institutions and authorities and in combination with the fact that the government of Chile had not declared an official demand for help, the situation was re-evaluated and was decided that a Task Force would not have to be sent to Chile for assistance. The ET returned to Greece in the following few days.

4.4 A WEAK SIGNAL APPROACH TO SCENARIO BUILDING

Weak Signals can be considered as past or emerging developments/issues, whose origin, meaning and/or implications may be ambiguously interpreted and can be potentially used as warning signs to possible future events. Weak signals may be defined as advanced indicators of change phenomena¹³⁸ and even though weak signals themselves are not clear-cut, they generally consist of information of an imperfect quality.¹³⁹ Examples of such cases may include changes in public attitudes or an emerging pattern of concern about emerging health problems. It is often said that weak signals lie in the eye of the observer and, due to their inherent subjectivity, their identification is considered as one of the most challenging tasks in future research¹⁴⁰.

Weak signals are emitted before crises actually occur but still organisations are not trained enough to detect them, learn from them and adapt to prevent a crisis¹⁴¹. Weak signals may offer valuable information, opportunities and hidden insight of a rising situation and after further examination may lead to actions-responses for early opportunity exploitation. They are everywhere so deciding when and where to keep the antennae out is critical. One such situation involves a product, market, or service that doesn't yet exist—but could. That is why it is useful to search for weak signals at the beginning of a situation, however, spotting them requires to have the time and space to do that (e.g. search through blogs, social media etc.).¹⁴² Identifying weak signals at an early stage can help even avoid or manage efficiently a crisis. However, as was mentioned before, checking for weak signals maybe too expensive¹⁴³, due to extensive man-hours required to be spotted and interpreted. Spotting a weak signal is also

¹³⁸ Sandro Mendonça, Gustavo Cardoso and João Caraça, “Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis”, LINI WORKING PAPERS N° 2, Lisbon Internet and Networks International Research Programmes, p.5, http://www.lini-research.org/np4/?newsId=9&fileName=SMENDONCA_ETAL_LINI_WP2.pdf

¹³⁹ Ibid., p.8

¹⁴⁰ <http://wiwe.iknowfutures.eu/what-is-a-weak-signal/>

¹⁴¹ Shari R. Veil, University of Kentucky, “Mindful Learning in Crisis Management”, Journal of Business Communication, Volume 48, Number 2, April 2011(p116-147) . p.116

¹⁴² Martin Harrysson, Estelle Métayer, and Hugo Sarrazin, February 2014, “The strength of weak signals”

¹⁴³“AT TIMES OF CRISIS, TWITTER SHINES BRIGHTEST”, <http://snurb.info/files/2012/Continuity.pdf>

more difficult, and is less likely to occur when information sources are not monitored by people who have a deep understanding of the business and act as listening posts. If spotted early and interpreted correctly, weak signals can lead to quick results, but just finding weak signals is not enough, since they must be interpreted and used correctly. Bottom line, the use of weak signals is a strategic decision for organisations, and, in any given situation, the responsibility for its application lies with the higher management.¹⁴⁴

Building a “weak signal” interpretative capability is a matter of continuous organisational development, namely in terms of assumption re-appraisal, sharing of perspectives, collective creativity, and prompt deliberation.¹⁴⁵ Societies actively ignore alarming information and this ultimately leads to ultimate crash.^{146, 147} Barriers to weak signal based strategising are greater than commonly appreciated. Doom rises not from the absence of information but from the stiffness of mindsets filtering out relevant data, discounting the severity of the warning and aborting the production of alternatives for changing the course of action.¹⁴⁸

4.4.1 How weak signals can influence foresight

The ability to identify networking correlations that lead to identifiable phenomena, prior to their occurrence, and not to take single phenomena as independent events is what weak signals actually stands for¹⁴⁹ and can thus lead to what we call *foresight* of events. Recently foresight has played an important role in the development and implementation of forward-looking research and innovation policies. However, “far too little attention has been paid to the identification and analysis of Wildcards and Weak Signals (WI-WE)”.¹⁵⁰ Thinking though about weak signals might help in acknowledging the limits of our foresight abilities as well as encourage new approaches that stretch the realm of the manageable but at the same time draw attention towards the creation of new long-term visions.^{151, 152, 153}

Even though strategic knowledge is widely dispersed, and often needs to be accessed through social networks, foresight can be instrumental in allowing intelligence strategists and policy-makers to act smoothly and avoid taking rushed and panicked decisions under the sudden shock of developments.¹⁵⁴ For example, in a situation where a weak signal related to an opportunity has been taken into account through an operational procedure it might induce positive results but, if not, negative results could be obtained in terms of various types of costs.¹⁵⁵

¹⁴⁴ Martin Harrysson, Estelle Métayer, and Hugo Sarrazin, February 2014, “The strength of weak signals”, http://www.mckinsey.com/insights/high_tech_telecoms_internet/the_strength_of_weak_signals

¹⁴⁵ Sandro Mendonça, Gustavo Cardoso and João Caraça, “Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis”, p.3

¹⁴⁶ Diamond, Jared (2004) “Twilight at Easter”, New York Review of Books, March 25, pp.

¹⁴⁷ Sandro Mendonça, et al, “Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis”, p.5

¹⁴⁸ Ibid.

¹⁴⁹ Sandro Mendonça, et al, “Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis”, p.10

¹⁵⁰ <http://wiwe.iknowfutures.eu/what-is-a-weak-signal/>

¹⁵¹ Ibid., p.5

¹⁵² Ibid., p.7.

¹⁵³ Keenan, Mike, Loveridge, Denis, Miles, Ian & Kaivo-oja, Jari (2003) Handbook of Knowledge Society Foresight. Prepared by PREST and FFRC for European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions. Final Report, European Foundation, Dublin, <http://www.eurofound.eu.int/publications/files/EF0350EN.pdf>

¹⁵⁴ Ibid., p.11

¹⁵⁵ Ibid., p.11

It has been proposed that “weak signal analysis, as a specific foresight methodology, can contribute to the emergence of a learning or adaptive policy-maker ideal-type both in private organisations and public administrations”, while it also holds true that making the most of “weak signals” is a double challenge of both collective perception and collective action, as is shown in Figure 5.^{156, 157}

Understanding how to detect weak signals and taking the next step of linking them to concrete action plans and responses, allows the organisation to “increase its internal strategic flexibility and actively reduce its external strategic vulnerability”.¹⁵⁸

Figure 5: Analytical and strategic issues connected to Weak Signals”¹⁵⁹

An example from the Haiti earthquake in January 2010 shows the loss of a weak signal via social media, and the value weak signals analysis can provide in similar future events.

Example: weak signals via social media in crisis¹⁶⁰.

“A July 2012 study demonstrated that real-time monitoring of Twitter messages in Haiti could have predicted the October/November 2010 cholera outbreaks two weeks earlier than they were detected. Anonymised data, shared by Digicel, demonstrated that population movements in response to the cholera outbreak began prior to official detection of the outbreak. Deaths from cholera are preventable and outbreaks are more easily dealt with in their early stages. This means there was a lost opportunity to save lives. While there is no way to arrive at a precise statistic, over 200 people had died by 23 October, four days after first detection, and 900 by 16 November. Overall, more than 6,000 people died and over 400,000 became ill”

¹⁵⁶ Ibid., p.13

¹⁵⁷ Metcalfe, S. (2002) “Equilibrium and evolutionary foundations of competition and technology policy: New perspectives on the division of labour and the innovation process”, mimeo.

¹⁵⁸ Ibid., p.17

¹⁵⁹ Sandro Mendonça, et al, “Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis”, p.14

¹⁶⁰ Alex Papadimitriou, Angelos Yannopoulos, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos, Rachel Finn, Kush Wadhwa, Hayley Watson, Lemi Baruh, “Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, COSMIC Deliverable D2.2, September 2013

4.4.2 Scenario building using weak signals and foresight

Weak signals, serving as advanced indicators that precede significant events have the potential to facilitate the real-time alignment between organisational decision-making and changing of external circumstances. The practical significance of weak signal information is that it can be transformed into meaningful knowledge for scenario building and to further extent policy actions as well as validate the scenarios themselves, as shown in Figure 6.¹⁶¹

Weak signals can be bundled, connected and presented into the form of scenarios, perhaps in a combination with strong signals, to decrease the complexity of an unpredictable future environment, facilitate the creation of future policies and help educate stakeholders regarding the implementation of those policies. “Successful organisations describe scenario building as an integral part of both their strategy development process and every business units’ continuous foresight process”.¹⁶²

Figure 6: Scenario Building¹⁶³

The basic contribution of a systematic weak signal analysis is to increase flexibility and to control for cognitive biases among decision-makers¹⁶⁴, which is the case of scenario building.

A standard scenario-building process as carried out by private firms to introduce a weak signal appraisal step, as shown in the figure below.

¹⁶¹ Ibid., p.2

¹⁶² Peter, Marc K. "Scenario Building and Future Screening – Strategic Corporate Foresight." Future Screening™ A Framework for Advancing Strategic Corporate Foresight. n.d. <http://futurescreening.com/foresight-framework/scenario-building/>.

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Sandro Mendonça, et al "Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis", p.12

Figure 3. Nesting weak signal research in foresight (e.g. scenario) projects.¹⁶⁵

As G. Cardoso put it, weak signal research is above all a process of structured networked communication.¹⁶⁶ It is this process of networking different information retrieved through different forms of mediation, together with focused discussion with regard to decision-making, which makes foresight useful for transforming weak signal information into more robust action plans.^{167, 168}

Using weak signal analysis to challenge non-conscious assumptions in individual decision-makers and to change previously established organisational agendas is a hard thing to do but that is ultimately the goal of an investment in probing the future, where useful foresight tools for understanding weak signals are linked to innovative strategising.¹⁶⁹

So far, we have seen of no evidence of weak signals been used as an aid to drawing crisis response scenarios for organisations. We still lack a coherent method for utilising such information in crises and this is certainly a new area for research.

4.5 CONCLUSION

Scenarios for emergency response have to be based on field experience and information available to rescue organisations taking part in the course of a crisis incident. To this end, in this chapter, we examined the basic aspects of such scenarios from three points of view:

- The organisation's mode of operation in specific events via their Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)
- The application of those to real-life situations as experienced by the COSMIC partner the Hellenic Rescue Team
- Newer theories based on weak signals and foresight, where we found a lack of systematic methods for application to crisis prediction and preparation scenarios

¹⁶⁵ Ibid., p.16

¹⁶⁶ Cardoso, Gustavo, "The Media in the Network Society", LuLu.com and CIES-ISCTE, 2007

¹⁶⁷ Sandro Mendonça, et al, "Some Notes on the Strategic Strength of Weak Signal Analysis", p.18

¹⁶⁸ Cardoso, Gustavo, "The Media in the Network Society", LuLu.com and CIES-ISCTE, 2007

¹⁶⁹ Ibid., p.21

In all categories, our findings point to the fact that the presence of social media appears particularly important. The establishment of a specific geographically distributed organisational unit per incident, dealing with digital communications and social media in particular, is foreseen in the SOPs of the US FEMA. This is supported by the real-life account of its role during Hurricane Sandy and the added application of a specific “rumour control” procedure. The additional evidence supplied by SOPs and the real-life situations confirmed that social media:

- Provide help towards responders by completing the building of situational awareness
- Are able to supply additional information, in particular at the first stages of a catastrophic incident, which can be decisive in attracting external funds and sponsoring and therefore enabling the participation of voluntary organisations (NGOs) such as the HRT
- Can provide valuable information able to direct rescuers of survivors
- Are a means of publishing information towards the public concerning rescue efforts and other vital to life information

Finally, we noted the need for further research in the utilisation of weak signals and foresight in drawing crisis response scenarios.

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5 CONCLUSION

We examined the use of new technologies to satisfy strategic communication goals of relevant stakeholders during crises. This was examined at three different levels, namely:

- among responders/law enforcement agencies
- between responders and the public
- among the public themselves

We identified four strategic goals relating to communication that are essential for stakeholders to be able to utilise communication to enhance their abilities to manage a crisis situation. These include: two-way communication, one-way communication/alerts, information sharing, and situational awareness. These goals should not be treated in isolation, but rather, should be considered in relation to one another as, under some circumstances, they are dependent on each other for enhancing crisis management. For instance, during a flood, in order for the public to assist responders in gaining situational awareness, information sharing (e.g., photographs or video content), two-way communication (e.g., being able to verify information, or request further information) are essential to building situational awareness which in turn can contribute to decision making to help coordinate response efforts.

Regarding the opportunities presented by social media technologies, our findings show that today we face a situation of “walled gardens” created and maintained by large platforms wanting to control information and to contain it among their members. The result is that proposed open standards have not gained widespread acceptance and true technical interoperability is still absent. Correspondingly, semantic interoperability, an even more difficult issue, is at an even less developed state. Partial solutions via the platforms’ APIs, however, have allowed some degree of inter-network communication and information retrieval, including users-related data. This has enabled the creation of a widely available number of network aggregator applications, which also has the beneficial effect of centralising social network information during a crisis. Another interesting development here is some advances on the semantic front. As crises have a relatively limited vocabulary, concepts and their inter-relations can be formalised as crisis ontologies and then utilised by (possibly specialised) social media applications.

Subsequently, we showed scenarios on how existing and emerging technologies, can potentially meet these inter-connected strategic goals for these stakeholder groups across the different phases of a crisis. We examined the basic aspects of such scenarios from three points of view:

- The organisation’s mode of operation in specific events via their Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)
- The application of those to real-life situations as experienced by the COSMIC partner the Hellenic Rescue Team
- Newer theories based on weak signals and foresight, where we found a lack of systematic methods for application to crisis prediction and preparation scenarios

In all categories, our findings point to the fact that the presence of social media appears particularly important in:

- The provision of help towards responders via supplementing the situational awareness picture
- Their ability to supply additional information, in particular at the first stages of a catastrophic incident, which can be decisive in attracting external funds and

sponsoring and therefore enabling the participation of voluntary organisations (NGOs) such as the HRT

- The supply of potentially valuable information able to direct rescuers of survivors
- Their role as a means of publishing information towards the public concerning rescue efforts and other vital to life information

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